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Microalgae strain catalogue

A strain selection guide for microalgae users: cultivation and chemical characteristics for high added-value products

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3rd Edition

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EnhanceMicroAlgae 2021

The 3rd edition of this catalogue contains information on the cultivation and composition characteristics of 37 microalgae. Each entry includes relevant links to Atlantic Area stakeholders known to have a relevant connection with each of the species listed, be it in the form of culture collections, research expertise, technology developers, or biomass producers. We invite the readers to visit and/or join the EnhanceMicroAlgae [Stakeholder database](#): an easily accessible, visual and open access database that brings together all the European Atlantic Area players working in the microalgae sector.

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Microalgae production for high added value compounds is identified as a business sector with high growth potential in the coming decades, especially in the Atlantic Area. Barriers to improve an industrial use are dominated by a lack of technology expertise.

*The **EnhanceMicroAlgae** project aims to stimulate research, innovation, industrial development and transnational cooperation within the Atlantic area microalgae sector. The main objective is to contribute to the competitiveness of microalgal-based industries in the Atlantic Area.*

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Introduction

Microalgae are a broad group of diverse microorganisms that are typically single-celled, photosynthetic organisms that derive from marine, brackish, freshwater or terrestrial environments. In this catalogue we include both eukaryotic and prokaryotic (cyanobacteria) species.

There is increasing commercial interest in the usage of microalgae for a wide variety of applications including animal feed, aquaculture, biofertiliser, waste pollutant remediation, sources of nutrients and chemicals for food production, nutraceutical supplements such as omega-3 fatty acids, cosmetics, biofuels and bioenergy, pharmaceutical products, colourings, antioxidants, flavourings, and other uses. These applications all depend on the characteristics and chemical composition of different microalgae species and strains.

It is estimated that there are many thousands of microalgae species with many different properties. In addition, strains of microalgae belonging to the same species or closely related species will have different characteristics and will have differences in their chemical composition due to living in different environments and adapting to the different physical conditions of that environment. Of these many possible strains, only a relatively small number have been collected and are stored within individual labs and in culture collections. Only a small number of strains of different species have been physiologically and biochemically characterised, and an even smaller number of strains are currently commercially used.

While the majority of available microalgae strains remain largely uncharacterised, a substantial amount of research has been performed on a small number of strains with desirable characteristics. However, strain characteristic information can be challenging to identify and is typically found within many different, sometime inaccessible literature sources. Therefore this resource has been developed in order to provide collated information on the cultivation characteristics and chemical composition of selected microalgae species.

Each entry summarises the characteristics of a different species, with details taken from one or more strains of that species, which are present in a publically accessible culture collection. As much details as possible about the cultivation procedures of the strains have been described so that the chemical composition characteristics might be reproducible. However, it must be noted, that strain properties can vary based on different environmental parameters and even between different locations where conditions are considered identical. Moreover, originally identical strains (from the same original source) can adapt their characteristics over time, therefore some caution must be taken when interpreting information assigned to a particular named strain.

We hope that you find this catalogue resource useful and informative. In addition, any feedback to this resource is welcome.

The EnhanceMicroAlgae team

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Important notes

- ⊗ The names of the microalgae species presented within this catalogue are in accordance with their currently accepted taxonomic status at the time of publication. However, names are subject to change as a result of new taxonomic discoveries. The reader is encouraged to refer to [AlgaeBase](#) for the most updated names and classification of microalgae.
- ⊗ Unless otherwise specified, it should be interpreted that cultivation data shown in the following pages was obtained during cultivation in batch operation and in phototrophic growth mode (using either air or artificial supplementation of CO₂).
- ⊗ A compilation of important algal growth media recipes shown throughout the catalogue is included in Appendix 1.
- ⊗ Similarly, a (non-exhaustive) list of major Culture Collections is provided in Appendix 2.

A list of common acronyms used throughout the catalogue is presented below:

Acronym	Description
PBR	Photobioreactor
nd	Non-disclosed
STR	Stirred Tank Reactor
L:D	Light:Dark cycle (photoperiod)
BG11	Blue-Green medium
BBM	Bold's Basal Medium

Definitions:

- ⊗ Lux (lx): A measure of radiant light from a standard candle that falls on one square meter of surface area one meter from the source.
- ⊗ Micromol (μmol/m²/s): One micromol per square meter per second. A unit of measure of the amount of light hitting a surface that is in the range of 400-700 nanometers.
- ⊗ Watts (W): Watts per square meter (W/m²). A unit of measure of the amount of light energy hitting a surface that is in the range of 400-800 nanometers.

1. *Anabaena cylindrica*

A freshwater filamentous cyanobacteria with robust growth characteristics and a source of pigments. It has nitrogen-fixation characteristics and some strains have been observed to produce hydrogen ¹.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 1403/2A, IAM M1 (PCC 7122), 10 C (CSMA)

1.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 1403/2A ²	System: PBR Medium: BG11 Temperature: 22°C Light: 70 μmol/m ² /s, 16 h L: 8 h D	0.078	0.171	2.4
IAM M1 (PCC 7122) ³	System: 5 PBR's in series (0.2 dm ³ each) Medium: Detmer medium Carbon source: CO ₂ 6% Temperature: 298 K (24.85°C) Light: 1 klx, L:D cycle N/A	nd	nd	From: 0.667 (1 st PBR) to: ~2.66 (5 th PBR)
10 C ⁴ (CSMA)	System: Fermentor (1 L) Medium: BG11 Carbon source: CO ₂ and acetate Temperature: 25°C Light: 32 W cool white fluorescent lamp. Continuous illumination	nd	nd	~0.3 (BG11) ~0.6 (BG11+acetate)
PCC 7937 ⁵	System: PBR (2 L) Medium: BG11 Temperature: 30°C Light: 3000 μmol/m ² /s, 12 h L: 12 h D	0.38 ± 0.14	nd	nd

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

1.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
56% protein ² 7% lipid 25% carbohydrate --- 38.09±1.18 % protein ⁵ 16.03±0.90 % lipid 37.07±2.26 % carbohydrate --- 43-56% protein ⁶ 4-7% lipid 25-30% carbohydrate	nd	nd	nd

1.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- ☼ **Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *A. cylindrica* AC163
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- ☼ **Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *A. cylindrica* CCAP 1403/2A, 1403/2B, 1403/30
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- ☼ **Name:** [Blue Biotechnology and Ecotoxicology Culture Collection \(LEGE\) at CIIMAR](#)
CIIMAR is an EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Anabena* cf. *cylindrica* LEGE 00235
 Read more about the services offered by the LEGE culture collection in the [EnhanceMicroAlgae marketplace](#).
Location: Porto, Portugal
- ☼ **Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *A. cylindrica* BEA 0794B

Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

⊗ **Name:** [IBVF - Instituto de Bioquímica Vegetal y Fotosíntesis, Microalgae Biotechnology Group](#)

Business/organisation type: research & development

Expertise: bioenergy, ecophysiology, molecular biology. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Anabaena* sp. ^{5,7}, *Porphyridium purpureum* ⁵, *Scenedesmus vacuolatus* ⁵, *Nostoc* ⁵, *Dunaliella salina* ⁸

Location: Sevilla, Spain

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2. *Ankistrodesmus falcatus*

A fast-growing freshwater microalga. It is considered an important source of lipids and pigments, and it can also accumulate a relatively high protein content ⁹.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCNM-1031, KJ671624, CMSACR1001

2.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
nd ¹⁰	System: 500 mL conical flasks Medium: BG-11, BBM, Chu-10, Zarrouk Temperature: 25 ± 2°C Light: 12h L: 12h D, at 30, 60 and 150 µmol/m ² /s; 12h L: 12h D, 18h L: 6h D, 6h L: 18h D, 24h L:0h D and 0h L: 24h D at 60 µmol/m ² /s	nd	6.14 mg/L/day (with BG-11 and Chu-10 media)	210.4 mg/L (with Zarrouk's medium)
nd ⁹	System: airlift photobioreactor Medium: BG-11 Temperature: below 30°C in batch and 36°C in continuous cultivation Carbon source: CO ₂ Light: 170 µmol/m ² /s in batch and 185 µmol/m ² /s in continuous cultivation, L:D cycle nd	nd	nd	1.04 (under batch cultivation) 1.56 (under continuous cultivation)

CMSACR1001 ¹¹	System: 1 L conical flask Medium: BG-11 Temperature: 25 ± 1 °C Light: 60 µmol/m ² /s, 12h L: 12h D	nd	0.035 (under phytohormones supplementation)	0.431 (under phytohormones supplementation)
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

2.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
16.23 – 57.70% lipids ⁹ --- 35% lipids ¹¹ 43% carbohydrates 17.5% proteins	nd	17.89 µg/mL total ¹¹ chlorophyll 2.65 µg/mL total carotenoids	C12:0 0.15-1.96% ⁹ C14:0 0.36-0.93% C16:0 28.87-40.66% C16:1 0.25-1.28% C18:0 3.93-6.38% C18:1 20.84-33.48% C18:2 8.01-18.90% C18:3(6) 0.19-0.97% C18:3(3) 3.30-18.70% C18:4 1.14-4.91% C24:0 0.06-3.50%

2.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

-
Name: [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *A. falcatus* CCAP 202/14A, 202/14B, 202/14C, 202/15C, 202/5C
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom

-
Name: [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Ankistrodesmus* sp. BEA 0536B, 1117B, 0742B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

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3. *Arthrospira platensis*

A filamentous cylindrical cyanobacteria that is commonly known commercially as spirulina. It is widely cultivated as a food source and nutritional supplement particularly because it is rich in protein and contains essential amino acids ¹². It is commonly cultivated in open ponds but can also be grown in photobioreactors. It can grow under a range of temperature conditions but has optimum growth at higher temperatures, ~35°C ¹³.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
SAG 21.99, SAG 85.79, SAG 257.80, WH879

3.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
SAG 85.79 ²	System: PBR Medium: Zarrouk medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 70 μmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	0.06	0.21	3.1
SAG 21.99 ¹⁴	System: PBR (0.5 L) Medium: Zarrouk medium Temperature: 30°C Light: 120 μmol/m ² /s, Continuous light	nd	0.231	2.274
Mixed culture: <i>Arthrospira</i> sp. ¹⁵	System: outdoor raceway ponds, surface area 100 m ² , culture depth 30 cm Medium: SOT medium Temperature: outdoors Light: outdoors	nd	34 (g/m ² /d, accounts for irradiance surface area)	0.62
WH879 ¹⁶	System: Fed-batch PBR (1 L) Medium: Zarrouk medium Temperature: 28°C Light: 300 μmol/m ² /s, Continuous light	nd	0.594 (feeding only Nitrate)	6.78 (feeding fresh medium)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

3.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
62% protein ² 9% lipid 20% carbohydrate	nd	90 mg/g phycocyanin ² 39.8 mg/g chlorophyll 3.8 mg/g carotene - - - 0.28-1.5% chlorophyll ¹⁴ - - - 5-12% phycocyanin ¹⁵ - - - 16.1±0.2% phycocyanin ¹⁶	C16:0 40.1% ² C16:1 9.2% C18:0 1.2% C18:1 5.4% C18:2 17.9% C18:3 18.3% other 7.9%

3.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- ☼ **Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *A. platensis* CH-9
Location: Roscoff, France
- ☼ **Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *A. platensis* BEA 0007B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain
- ☼ **Name:** [A4F – Algae 4 Future](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: bio-bank, producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Their microalgae track-production (large and pilot scale) includes ¹⁷:
 - *Arthrospira platensis*, *Chlamydomonas* sp., *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Dunaliella salina*, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Lobosphaera incisa*, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Prorocentrum cassubicum*, *Raphidonema* sp., *Scenedesmus* sp., *Scotiellopsis* sp., *Synechococcus* sp., *Synechocystis* sp., *Tetraselmis* sp., *Thalassiosira weissflogii*, *Tisochrysis lutea*

Locations: Lisbon, Portugal

⊗ **Name:** [Algalimento](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated partner

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Algalimento currently produces all-year round high-quality biomass of ¹⁸:

- *Tetraselmis sp., Spirulina canariensis, Dunaliella salina*

Locations: Lisbon, Portugal

⊗ **Name:** [AlgoSource](#)

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: engineering, large-scale development, industrial ecology. Know-how on *Spirulina* and its principal ingredient phycocyanin. The company is also working on extracting molecules of interest from other microalgae ¹⁹:

- *Spirulina, Chlorella, Scenedesmus, Tetraselmis, Isochrysis*

Locations: Saint-Nazaire, France

⊗ **Name:** [Aqualgae](#)

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: design and installation of high-productivity photobioreactors, suppliers of culturing media, inoculums, and lyophilised cultures of ²⁰:

- *Chlorella, Haematococcus, Arthrospira, Tetraselmis, Isochrysis, Pavlova, Chaetoceros, Skeletonema, Nitzschia, Rhodomonas, Nannochloropsis*

Locations: Diana do Castelo, Portugal; and A Coruña, Spain

⊗ **Name:** [Bretagne Sipurline](#)

Business/organisation type: producer

Expertise: nutraceuticals. The company sells *Spirulina* in various pack sizes.

Locations: Landévant, France

⊗ **Name:** [International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory \(INL\)](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: nanotechnology, nanoscience, encapsulation, food processing and nutrition, nutraceuticals, safety assessment, biotechnology, engineering. Research outputs include (but not limited to):

- *Arthrospira platensis* ²¹

Locations: Braga, Portugal

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- ⊗ **Name:** [La Voie Bleue](#)
Business/organisation type: association
Expertise: marketing and valorisation, nutraceuticals, sustainable food chains. Promotes Spirulina (and other microalgae) for food by local production, and supports other projects. Read about La Voie Bleue's services in the [EnhanceMicroAlgae marketplace](#)
Locations: Toulouse, France

- ⊗ **Name:** [NeoAlgae](#)
Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: aquaculture, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. The company produces a wide range of Spirulina-based products for food, cosmetics, and agriculture ²². Their R&D division specialises on various extracts from *Dunaliella salina*, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Isochrysis galbana*, *Nannochloropsis gaditana* ²³
Locations: Asturias, Spain

- ⊗ **Name:** [OMA – Olivier MicroAlgues](#)
Business/organisation type: producer, downstream processing
Expertise: nutraceuticals. The company sells *Spirulina* in various packs and formats.
Location: Haute-Goulaine, France

- ⊗ **Name:** [Spanish Society of Microalgae and Subproducts](#) (SEMS)
Business/organisation type: producer, research and development
Expertise: biotechnology, chemistry, marketing and valorisation. The company offers various laboratory services and products for agriculture, with various microalgae being produced on a continuous basis ²⁴:
 - *Arthrospira platensis*, *Nannochloropsis gaditana*, *Scenedesmus* sp., and *Scenedesmus subspicatus***Locations:** Rota, Spain

- ⊗ **Name:** [Scottish Bioenergy Ltd.](#)
Business/organisation type: producer, technology manufacturer, downstream processing
Expertise: energy, environment, biotechnology. Company products include a Spirulina-based colourant (ScotBio Blue) and protein (ScotBio protein), as well as fresh/dry Spirulina.
Locations: Newhouse, Scotland

- ⊗ **Name:** [Technature](#)
Business/organisation type: research and development
Expertise: cosmetics. The company offers a wide line of cosmetic products, some of which are derived from Spirulina extracts (e.g. Toning lotion, Radiance boost marine serum, algae heating body wrap) ²⁵
Locations: Dirinon, France

⊗ **Name:** [Tinctura](#)

Business/organisation type: producer, downstream processing

Expertise: nutraceuticals, large-scale development. Tinctura develops and produces aqueous extracts rich in phycocyanin from French Spirulina.

Locations: Ploudaniel, France

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4. *Auxenochlorella protothecoides*

Formerly known as *Chlorella protothecoides* (Krüger) ²⁶. A eukaryotic green microalga belonging to Trebouxiophyceae class. It can grow either photoautotrophically, mixotrophically or heterotrophically ²⁷. *C. protothecoides* shows a high industrial potential for producing lipids and fatty acids at high yield ²⁸.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
UTEX 249, SAG 211-7b

4.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
UTEX 249 ²⁷	System: 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks Medium: BBM Carbon source: glucose, glycerol, or acetate Light: 16h L: 8h D (autotrophic and mixotrophic) and 24h D (heterotrophic)	nd	1.59±0.50 (on glucose/acetate; 80:20)	4.76±1.50 (on glucose/acetate; 80:20)
nd ²⁸	System: 2.8 L glass flasks (PYREX) Medium: Modified BBM Temperature: 28°C Carbon source: CO ₂ , and glucose Light: 60 μmol m ⁻² s ⁻¹ L:D cycle nd	nd	nd	9.54 ± 0.72 (mixotrophic cultures) 10.32 ± 0.83 (heterotrophic cultures)
nd ²⁹ obtained from Culture Collection of Alga at the University of Texas	System: Shaking flasks / 5 L bioreactor Medium: BBM Temperature: 28°C Carbon source: glucose Light: 5 μmol/m ² /s L:D cycle nd	nd	nd	51.2 (in improve fed-batch culture)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

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4.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
52% lipids ²⁷	nd	nd	nd

4.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- 🌐 **Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *A. protothecoides* CCAP 211/11I, 211/13, 211/17, 211/54, 211/7A, 2117C, 211/7D, 211/8D
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom

5. *Botryococcus braunii*

A eukaryotic planktonic Trebouxiophyceae strain, naturally found in freshwater and brackish ponds, that is typically a very slow growing microalga due to the high production of triterpene hydrocarbon oils with applications for various classes of biofuel (petroleum, kerosene, diesel) production by hydrocracking. There are a wide variety of *Botryococcus* strains (races) with very diverse oil productivities³⁰.

Commonly cultivated strains include:

CCAP 807/2, SAG 30.81, CCALA 777, CCALA 778, CCALA 835, UTEX Bb 572, AC755, AC759, AC760, AC761, AC765³¹

5.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 807/2 ²	System: PBR Medium: 3N-BBM Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 μmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	0.027	0.098	1.94
AC755 ³¹	System: Bubble column PBR (0.4 L) Medium: Chu 13 medium Temperature: 23°C Light: 150 μmol/m ² /s, 18h L: 6h D	nd	0.06	~1.75
AC759			0.09	~2.75
AC761			0.15	~3.6
CCALA 777			0.08	~2.2
CCALA 778			0.12	~3.6
CCAP 807/2			0.14	~4.6

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

5.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
40% protein ² 33% lipid 6% carbohydrate	nd	6% α -carotene ³² 6% β -carotene 22% lutein	C16:0 29.5% ² C16:1 3.3% C18:0 1.0% C18:1 44.9% C18:2 21.1% other 0.3%

5.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- ☼ **Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *B. braunii* AC754, AC755 to AC761, AC763, AC767, AC768
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- ☼ **Name:** [Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa CCAP](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *B. braunii* 807/1, 807/2
Location: Scottish Marine institute, Scotland, UK
- ☼ **Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Botryococcus* sp. A12.415 (not-distributed), A13-394 (not-distributed), CCMP2742
Location: Roscoff, France
- ☼ **Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *B. braunii* BEA 0649B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

⊗ **Name:** [Andalusian Center of Science and Marine Technology](#) (CACYTMAR) | [Instituto Universitario de Investigacion Marina](#) (INMAR) at University of Cádiz, Spain

Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development

Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology, genomics, molecular biology, waste water treatment. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Botryococcus braunii*³³, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*³⁴, [*Chlorella vulgaris*, *Chlorella kessleri*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Scenedesmus obliquus*]³⁵

Location: Cádiz, Spain

6. *Chaetoceros calcitrans*

A marine planktonic diatom. It is a roughly cylindrical alga, elliptical in valve view and rectangular in girdle view. The cells bear long cell wall prolongations (seta) at their poles which join cells together to form chains.

C. calcitrans (Paulsen) Takano is known as a potential species for producing biodiesel³⁶, with high growth rates even at low light intensities³⁷.

Commonly cultivated strains include:

CCMP 60/00/00 1315, CCAP 1010/11, CCMP1315; NEPCC 590; PLY537, UPMAAHU10.

6.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCMP 60/00/00 1315 ³⁷	System: 16-29 L bags Medium: Conway Carbon source: 0.2% CO ₂ Temperature: 20-23°C Light: 750–1000 lx, continuous light	nd	nd	7-13x10 ⁶ cells/mL
UPMAAHU10 ³⁸	System: 1 L flasks (outdoors and lab) Medium: Conway Temperature: 24-36°C (outdoors); 23°C (lab) Light: 140 μmol/m ² /s, 12h L: 12h D (outdoors); 150 μmol/m ² /s, 12h L: 12h D (lab).	nd	nd	2.50±0.20 (outdoors) 2.20±0.10 (lab)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

6.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
Protein: ³⁸ - 41.60% (outdoors); - 43.10% (lab) Lipid: - 26.80% (outdoors); - 11.71% (lab) Carbohydrate: - 8.70% (outdoors); - 6.62% (lab)	nd	nd	C14:0 18.0% ³⁷ C16:0 13.6% ΣSFA 34.4% C16:1(n-7) 27.6% C18:1 (n-9) 0.7% ΣMUFA 30.0% C18:3 (n-3) 0.1% C18:4 (n-3) 2.1% EPA 16.3% DHA 0.4% Σ(n-3) 19.1% 16:3 (n-4) 14.6% 18:2 (n-6) 0.4% ΣPUFA 35.6%

6.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- ☉ **Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *C. calcitrans* AC165
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France

- ☉ **Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *C. calcitrans* Arg 11, Arg 13, *Chaetoceros* sp.
Location: Roscoff, France

- ☉ **Name:** [Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa CCAP](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *C. calcitrans* 1085/3
Location: Scottish Marine institute, Scotland, UK

- ☉ **Name:** [ANFACO-CECOPESCA](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae project Lead Coordinator

Business/organisation type: Marketing, research & development and innovation support in food and marine technology.

Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology, marketing, valorisation and functionality of microalgal compounds. Microalgal expertise includes (not limited to) ^{39,40}:

- ***Chaetoceros calcitrans***, *C. salsugineus*, *Conticribra weissflogii* (synonym of *Thalassiosira weissflogii*), *Isochrysis galbana*, *Nannochloropsis gaditana*, *Pavlova gyrams*, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Rhodomonas lens*, *Tetraselmis chuii*, *Tisochrysis lutea*

ANFACO-CECOPECA offers production of tailor-made microalgal biomass. Read more in the [EnhanceMicroAlgae marketplace](#).

Location: Vigo, Spain

⊗ **Name:** [Aqualgae](#)

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: design and installation of high-productivity photobioreactors, suppliers of culturing media, inoculums, and lyophilised cultures of ²⁰:

- *Chlorella*, *Haematococcus*, *Arthrospira*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*, *Pavlova*, ***Chaetoceros***, *Skeletonema*, *Nitzschia*, *Rhodomonas*, *Nannochloropsis*

Locations: Diana do Castelo, Portugal; and A Coruña, Spain

⊗ **Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Alexandrium minutum* ⁴¹, *Alexandrium tamarense* ⁴¹, *Bigeloviella natans* ⁴¹, ***Chaetoceros calcitrans*** ⁴¹, ***Chaetoceros calcitrans f. pumillum*** ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros gracilis* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros minus* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros mulleri* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros sp. Tenuissimus like* ⁴¹, *Chlorella autotrophica* ⁴¹, *Chlorella vulgaris* ⁴¹, *Chloroarchnion reptans* ⁴¹, *Closterium baillyanum* ⁴¹, *Cyanophora paradoxa* ^{41,42}, *Cylindrotheca closterium* ⁴³, *Dunaliella salina* ^{41,44}, *Dunaliella sp.* ⁴¹, *Dunaliella tertiolecta* ^{41,45}, *Emiliania huxleyi* ⁴¹, *Haematococcus pluvialis* ⁴¹, *Heterocapsa triquetra* ⁴⁶, *Isochrysis galbana* ⁴¹, *Nitzschia sp.* ⁴¹, *Odontella aurita* ⁴¹, *Ostreococcus tauri* ⁴¹, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* ⁴¹, *Porphyridium purpureum* (*Porphyridium cruentum*) ^{44,47,48}, *Rhodella violacea* ⁴¹, *Rhodomonas salina* ^{41,49}, *Scenedesmus acutus* ⁴¹, *Scenedesmus obliquus* ⁴¹, *Skeletonema grethae* ⁴¹, *Tetraselmis suecica* ⁴¹, *Thalassiosira pseudonana* ⁴¹, *Tisochrysis lutea* ⁵⁰, *Euglena proxima* ⁴¹

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina* (*A. platensis*), from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

⊗ **Name:** [Xanthella Ltd.](#)

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Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Design and test bespoke PBRs, consultancy, repair and recycling of old systems, active research and development. The company has worked on ⁵¹:

- *Chaetoceros muelleri*, *Chlamydomonas acidophila*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Dunaliella primolecta*, *Desmodesmus subspicatus*, *Fragilaria* sp., *Isochrysis galbana*, *Limnorphis robusta*, *Nannochloropsis* sp., *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Porphyridium cruentum*, *Synechocystis* sp., *T-isochrysis lutea*

Location: European Marine Science Park, Argyll, Scotland

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7. *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*

A photosynthetic biflagellate microalga (Chlorophyta) that has been studied for more than 30 years as a model for basic and applied physiology and biochemistry, partly due to its ease of culturing and the ability to manipulate its genetics ⁵². It can be cultivated photoautotrophically and also heterotrophically or mixotrophically ⁵³. Commercially, it is of interest for producing biopharmaceuticals and biofuel, as well being a valuable research tool in making hydrogen.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
UTEX 90, CC-124, CC-125

7.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
UTEX 90 ⁵⁴	System: Flat-vertical PBR Medium: minimal medium Carbon source: glacial acetic acid with supplemental CO ₂ Temperature: 25-28°C Light: outdoor light conditions during May to July 2003 in Dae-jeon, Korea.	nd	nd	1.45 (fresh) 12-18 (concentrated)
CC-124 ⁵⁵ wild-type mt(-) 137c	System: flask on a rotatory shaker Medium: TAP medium Carbon source: acetic acid Temperature: 23 °C Light: 150 μmol/m ² /s, continuous light	nd	nd	~1.25x10 ⁷ cells/mL
CC-125 ⁵⁵ wild-type mt(+) 137c	System: flask on a rotatory shaker Medium: TAP medium Carbon source: acetic acid Temperature: 23 °C Light: 150 μmol/m ² /s, continuous light	nd	nd	~1.10x10 ⁷ cells/mL

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

7.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
CC-124 ⁵⁵ 16.8% lipid in Control 39.8% lipid in N-starvation 37.6% lipid in S-starvation	Autotrophic ⁵⁶ 48.1% C 5.8% N 7.3% H 38.8% O		
CC-125 14.2% lipid in Control 41.4% lipid in N-starvation 39.7% lipid in S-starvation	Mixotrophic 50.7% C 3.5% N 7.9% H 37.9% O	Autotrophic ⁵⁶ 0.9% Chlorophyll-a 1.5% Chlorophyll-b	C14:0 0.8% ⁵⁷ C16:0 24% C16:1 1.9% C16:2 1.2% C16:3 0.9% C18:0 5.2% C18:1 23.5% C18:2 15.4% C18:3 21.6% C20:4 0.5% C20:5 4.9% C22:0 0.2%
--- <i>Autotrophic</i> ⁵⁶ 26.1% protein 18.9% lipid 50.8% carbohydrate	Heterotrophic 50.5% C 10.5% N 7.7% H 31.3% O	Mixotrophic 0.7% Chlorophyll-a 1.3% Chlorophyll-b	
<i>Heterotrophic</i> 22.2% protein 28.7% lipid 44.8% carbohydrate		Heterotrophic 1.8% Chlorophyll-a 0.8% Chlorophyll-b	Σ SFA=30.2 Σ MUFA=25.4 Σ PUFA=44.5

7.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- ☉ **Name:** [Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa CCAP](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *C. reinhardtii* 11/32A, 11/32B, 11/32C, 11/32CW15+, 11/45
Location: Scottish Marine institute, Scotland, UK
- ☉ **Name:** [A4F – Algae 4 Future](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: bio-bank, producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Their microalgae track-production (large and pilot scale) includes ¹⁷:

- *Arthrospira platensis*, ***Chlamydomonas* sp.**, *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Dunaliella salina*, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Lobosphaera incisa*, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*, *Phaeodactylum tricorutum*, *Prorocentrum cassubicum*, *Raphidonema* sp., *Scenedesmus* sp., *Scotiellopsis* sp., *Synechococcus* sp., *Synechocystis* sp., *Tetraselmis* sp., *Thalassiosira weissflogii*, *Tisochrysis lutea*

Locations: Lisbon, Portugal

- ⊗ **Name:** [Department of Chemical and Biological Engineering, The University of Sheffield](#)

Network: [Algal Biotechnology Sheffield Network](#)

Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.

Expertise: Research outputs with microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Scenedesmus subspicatus* ⁶⁴, ***Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*** ^{61,65}, *Dunaliella salina* ⁶⁵⁻⁶⁷, *Micractinium inermum* ⁶⁵, *Chlorella vulgaris* ^{68,69}, *Phaeodactylum tricorutum* ^{70,71}, *Nannochloropsis salina* ⁶⁶, *Nannochloropsis oceanica* ⁷¹

Location: Sheffield, UK

- ⊗ **Name:** [Microalgae group at Centro de Investigaciones Científicas Avanzadas \(CICA\), University of A Coruña](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Partner

Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.

Expertise: chemistry, ecophysiology, genomics, monitoring. Research outputs involving microalgae at University of A Coruña include (but are not limited to):

- ***Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*** ⁷², *Dunaliella salina* ⁷³, *Haematococcus pluvialis* ⁷⁴

Location: A Coruña, Spain

- ⊗ **Name:** [MicroSynbiotix](#)

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Aquaculture, medical.

Aiming to reduce antibiotics use in farmed seafood, the company is researching how microalgae can be employed as a delivery transport of recombinant proteins to fish. P-o-C (proof-of-concept) research with *C. reinhardtii* ⁷⁵.

Locations: Cork, Ireland and San Diego California, USA

- ⊗ **Name:** [University of Manchester](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Partner

Business/organization type: Higher education, research & development.

Expertise: bioenergy, biotechnology, molecular biology, engineering, mathematical models. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

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- *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*^{76–79}, *Chlamydomonas acidophila*⁸⁰, *Haematococcus pluvialis*⁸¹, *T-isochrysis lutea*⁸², *Pseudanabaena catenata*⁸³

Location: Manchester, UK

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8. *Chlorella sorokiniana*

A eukaryotic freshwater Trebouxiophyceae strain with fast growth rate with applications for animal feed, nutritional supplement, and biofuel. It can be cultivated autotrophically, mixotrophically or heterotrophically^{84, 85}. Some *C. sorokiniana* show a broad temperature range and thermotolerance up to 45°C⁸⁶.

Commonly cultivated strains include:

UTEX 1230, UTEX 1602, UTEX 3016, UTEX 2805, IBVF 211-32

8.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
UTEX 1230 ²	System: PBR Medium: 3N-BBM Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 μmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	0.115	0.185	3.7
IBVF 211-32 ⁸⁷	System: 2 L stirred tank reactor (STR) Medium: Sueoka medium Carbon source: CO ₂ , and acetate Temperature: 25°C Light: 100 μmol/m ² /s, Continuous light	nd	1.16	1.18 (on CO ₂) ~3.1 (on acetate)
UTEX 1602 ⁸⁸	System: 250 mL flasks Medium: Kuhl medium Carbon source: 1 % CO ₂ , glucose Temperature: 25°C Light: 100 μmol/m ² /s, Continuous light	nd	nd	0.68 (on CO ₂) 5.08 (on glucose)
UTEX 2805 ⁸⁹	System: 250 mL flasks Medium: synthetic medium Temperature: 27°C Light: 60 μmol/m ² /s, L:D cycle nd	nd	nd	2.11±0.26 x 10 ⁶ (cell/mL)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

8.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
56% protein ² 22% lipid 17% carbohydrate --- 6.65% lipids (on CO ₂) ⁸⁸ 31.58% lipids (on glucose) --- 40% lipids ⁸⁷	46% C ² 2% N C/N ratio 21	32.4 mg/g total chlorophyll ² 1.2 mg/g beta-carotene 7.1 mg/g lutein	C16:0 22.0% ² C16:1 4.3% C16:2 11.5% C16:3 5.1% C18:0 3.5% C18:1 11.3% C18:2 31.1% C18:3 9.1% other 2.1% --- C16:0 20.99% ⁸⁸ C16:1 5.56% C16:2 4.82% C18:0 0.33% C18:1 2.95% C18:2 13.79% C18:3 33.31%

Additional biomass considerations:

Supplementation of glucose as a carbon source can increase cell density, biomass production and total lipid yield but decreases protein abundance and chlorophyll biosynthesis ²⁹.

8.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

-
Name: [Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa CCAP](#)
Business/organisation: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *C. sorokiniana* 211/8K
Location: Scottish Marine institute, Scotland, UK

-
Name: [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *C. sorokiniana* BEA 0002 to 0004, BEA 0022, BEA 0302, BEA 0665B, BEA 0061, BEA 0665B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

-
Name: [Andalusian Center of Science and Marine Technology](#) (CACYTMAR) | [Instituto Universitario de Investigacion Marina](#) (INMAR) at University of Cádiz, Spain
Business/organisation: Higher education, research & development
Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology, genomics, molecular biology, waste water treatment. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Botryococcus braunii*³³, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*³⁴, [*Chlorella vulgaris*, *Chlorella kessleri*, ***Chlorella sorokiniana***, *Scenedesmus obliquus*]³⁵

Location: Cádiz, Spain

- ⊗ **Name:** [Laboratoire GENie des Procédés Environnement – Agroalimentaire, GEPEA](#)

Business/organisation: research and development, higher education

Expertise: bioenergy, biotechnology, chemistry, engineering. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Chlorella vulgaris*⁹⁰, ***Chlorella sorokiniana***⁹¹, *Parachlorella kessleri*⁹², *Nannochloropsis oculata*⁹⁰

Location: Saint-Nazaire, France

- ⊗ **Name:** [Xanthella Ltd.](#)

Business/organisation: research and development

Expertise: Design and test bespoke PBRs, consultancy, repair and recycling of old systems, active research and development. The company has worked on⁵¹:

- *Chaetoceros muelleri*, *Chlamydomonas acidophila*, ***Chlorella sorokiniana***, *Dunaliella primolecta*, *Desmodesmus subspicatus*, *Fragilaria* sp., *Isochrysis galbana*, *Limnoraphis robusta*, *Nannochloropsis* sp., *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Porphyridium cruentum*, *Synechocystis* sp., *T-isochrysis lutea*

Location: European Marine Science Park, Argyll, Scotland

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9. *Chlorella vulgaris*

A eukaryotic marine Trebouxiophyceae strain that has large-scale commercial cultivation in Asia as a high protein-rich food and feed source, a nutritional supplement, and biofuel source. It can be cultivated autotrophically, mixotrophically or heterotrophically^{93–95}. It has quite robust growth for cultivation in open ponds as well as photobioreactors⁹⁶.

Commonly cultivated strains include:

CCAP 211/8K, CCAP 211/11B, CCAP 211/21A, CCAP 211/21B, CCAP 211/79, UTEX 2805, UTEX 2714

9.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 211/79 ²	System: PBR Medium: Jaworski's medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 16h L: 8h D	0.18	0.428	3.0
UTEX 2805 ⁸⁹	System: 250 mL flasks Medium: synthetic medium Temperature: 27°C Light: 60 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, L:D cycle nd	nd	nd	$3.2 \pm 0.5 \times 10^6$ cell/mL
UTEX 2714 ⁹⁷	System: 250 mL flasks Medium: modified/optimised synthetic medium Carbon source: glucose/glycerol Temperature: 26°C Light: 60 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, L:D cycle nd	nd	1.87	5.62
nd ⁹⁸ purchased from Connecticut Valley Biological Supply Co. Inc	System: PBR (3.8 gallon, 6 L working volume) Medium: BBM Temperature: 25°C Light: 276 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, L:D cycle nd	nd	0.35	~1.6

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

9.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
58% protein ² 12% lipid 17% carbohydrate ---	52% C ² 3% N C/N ratio 19	22.6 mg/g total chlorophyll ² 2.7 mg/g total carotenoid	C14:0 3.1% ² C16:0 25.1% C16:1 5.3% C16:3 1.3% C18:0 0.6% C18:1 12.6% C18:2 7.2% C18:3 19.1% C20:3 0.8% other 24%
51-58% protein ⁶ 14-22% lipid 12-17% carbohydrate ---			---
40.10% lipid ⁹⁷			C14:0 3.01% ⁹⁹ C16:0 16.99% C16:1 13.61% C16:2 5.47% C16:3 7.93% C18:0 1.51% C18:1 8.55% C18:2 14.44% C18:3 16.63% C20:4 1.24% C20:5 10.17%

9.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- **Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *C. vulgaris* AC149, AC150, AC873
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- **Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: multiple, including *C. vulgaris* 211/21A, 211/21B, 211/109 to 211/114, 211/79 to 211/82
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- **Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *C. vulgaris* BEA 0753B, BEA 0755B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

- ⊗ **Name:** [Algal Research Group, Swansea University](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.

Expertise: Microalgae biotechnology, biomass characterization, upstream and downstream process, chemistry, ecophysiology, engineering, large-scale development, molecular biology. Research expertise with microalgae includes (but is not limited to):

- *Scenedesmus obliquus* and ***Chlorella vulgaris*** ⁵⁸, *Arthrospira maxima* ⁵⁹, *Nannochloropsis spp.* ⁶⁰, *Micractinum inermum* ⁶¹, *Porphyridium purpureum* ^{62,63}, *Nosctoc sp.*, *Isochrysis galbana* and over 25 common microalgae species including green algae, diatoms, cyanobacteria and dinoflagellates.

Location: Swansea, UK

- ⊗ **Name:** [A4F – Algae 4 Future](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated partner

Business/organisation type: bio-bank, producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Their microalgae track-production (large and pilot scale) includes ¹⁷:

- *Arthrospira platensis*, *Chlamydomonas sp.*, ***Chlorella vulgaris***, *Dunaliella salina*, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Lobosphaera incisa*, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*, *Phaeodactylum tricorutum*, *Prorocentrum cassubicum*, *Raphidonema sp.*, *Scenedesmus sp.*, *Scotiellopsis sp.*, *Synechococcus sp.*, *Synechocystis sp.*, *Tetraselmis sp.*, *Thalassiosira weissfloi*, *Tisochrysis lutea*

Locations: Lisbon, Portugal

- ⊗ **Name:** [AlgoSource](#)

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: engineering, large-scale development, industrial ecology. Know-how on *Spirulina* and its principal ingredient phycocyanin. The company is also working on extracting molecules of interest from other microalgae ¹⁰⁰:

- *Spirulina*, ***Chlorella***, *Scenedesmus*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*

Locations: Saint-Nazaire, France

- ⊗ **Name:** [Andalusian Center of Science and Marine Technology](#) (CACYTMAR) | [Instituto Universitario de Investigacion Marina](#) (INMAR) at University of Cádiz, Spain

Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development

Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology, genomics, molecular biology, waste water treatment. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Botryococcus braunii* ³³, *Phaeodactylum tricorutum* ³⁴, [***Chlorella vulgaris***, *Chlorella kessleri*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Scenedesmus obliquus*] ³⁵

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Location: Cádiz, Spain

⊗ **Name:** [Aqualgae](#)

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: design and installation of high-productivity photobioreactors, suppliers of culturing media, inoculums, and lyophilised cultures of ²⁰:

- *Chlorella*, *Haematococcus*, *Arthrospira*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*, *Pavlova*, *Chaetoceros*, *Skeletonema*, *Nitzschia*, *Rhodomonas*, *Nannochloropsis*

Locations: Diana do Castelo, Portugal; and A Coruña, Spain

⊗ **Name:** [Biorea](#)

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: Aquaculture; Cosmetics; Feed; Food; Nutraceuticals; Biotechnology. They specialise in *Chlorella* production, but support customers with R&D and production of tailor-made biomass in their patented airlift bioreactors. See their market offer in the [EnhanceMicroAlgae marketplace](#).

Locations: Lamballe, France

⊗ **Name:** [Buggypower](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated partner

Business/organization type: producer, research & development, downstream processing

Expertise: feed, food, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. The company specialises in ¹⁰¹:

- *Chlorella*, *Nannochloropsis*, *Rhodomonas*

Location: Lisbon, Portugal (shared services centre & Alguimya store); Funchal, Portugal (Financial office); Porto Santo, Portugal (Buggypower production unit in partnership with Electricity Company of Madeira); San Pedro del Pinatar, Spain (Financial office); Lorqui, Spain (Research and development pilot plant)

⊗ **Name:** [Department of Chemical and Biological Engineering, The University of Sheffield](#)

Network: [Algal Biotechnology Sheffield Network](#)

Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.

Expertise: Research outputs with microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Scenedesmus subspicatus* ⁶⁴, *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* ^{61, 65}, *Dunaliella salina* ⁶⁵⁻⁶⁷, *Micractinium inermum* ⁶⁵, *Chlorella vulgaris* ^{68, 69}, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* ^{70, 71}, *Nannochloropsis salina* ⁶⁶, *Nannochloropsis oceanica* ⁷¹

Location: Sheffield, UK

⊗ **Name:** [Laboratoire GENie des Procédés Environnement – Agroalimentaire, GEPEA](#)

Business/organisation type: research and development, higher education

Expertise: bioenergy, biotechnology, chemistry, engineering. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

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- ***Chlorella vulgaris***⁹⁰, *Chlorella sorokiniana*⁹¹, *Parachlorella kessleri*⁹², *Nannochloropsis oculata*⁹⁰

Location: Saint-Nazaire, France

- ⊗ **Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Alexandrium minutum*⁴¹, *Alexandrium tamarense*⁴¹, *Bigelowiella natans*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans f. pumillum*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros gracilis*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros minus*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros mulleri*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros sp. Tenuissimus like*⁴¹, *Chlorella autotrophica*⁴¹, ***Chlorella vulgaris***⁴¹, *Chloroarchnion reptans*⁴¹, *Closterium baillyanum*⁴¹, *Cyanophora paradoxa*^{41,42}, *Cylindrotheca closterium*⁴³, *Dunaliella salina*^{41,44}, *Dunaliella sp.*⁴¹, *Dunaliella tertiolecta*^{41,45}, *Emiliania huxleyi*⁴¹, *Haematococcus pluvialis*⁴¹, *Heterocapsa triquetra*⁴⁶, *Isochrysis galbana*⁴¹, *Nitzschia sp.*⁴¹, *Odontella aurita*⁴¹, *Ostreococcus tauri*⁴¹, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁴¹, *Porphyridium purpureum (Porphyridium cruentum)*^{44,47,48}, *Rhodella violacea*⁴¹, *Rhodomonas salina*^{41,49}, *Scenedesmus acutus*⁴¹, *Scenedesmus obliquus*⁴¹, *Skeletonema grethae*⁴¹, *Tetraselmis suecica*⁴¹, *Thalassiosira pseudonana*⁴¹, *Tisochrysis lutea*⁵⁰, *Euglena proxima*⁴¹

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina (A. platensis)*, from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

- ⊗ **Name:** [NeoAlgae](#)

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: aquaculture, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. The company produces a wide range of **Spirulina**-based products for food, cosmetics, and agriculture¹⁰². Their R&D division specialises on various extracts from¹⁰³:

- *Dunaliella salina*, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, ***Chlorella vulgaris***, *Isochrysis galbana*, *Nannochloropsis gaditana*¹⁰³

Locations: Asturias, Spain

- ⊗ **Name:** [Research and training centre of LLDC Algae](#)

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: large-scale development. Their range of products include *Chlorella*-based animal feed (Greenfeed¹⁰⁴) and vitamin B12 for human use (Greenbloom¹⁰⁵).

Locations: Bréhan, France

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10. *Chromochloris zofingiensis*

Formerly known as *Chlorella zofingiensis* (Dönn) ²⁶. A freshwater green microalga. It can grow phototrophically, heterotrophically and mixotrophically, and it is easy to be cultured and scaled up both indoors and outdoors, achieving high cell density. It is considered a potential alternative for astaxanthin production ¹⁰⁶.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
UTEX B32

10.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
nd ¹⁰⁷	System: 300 mL glass PBRs Medium: BG11 Carbon source: 5% CO ₂ Temperature: 25°C Light: 300 μmol/m ² /s, continuous light	nd	nd	2.50
UTEX B32 ¹⁰⁸	System: Flat-panel, airlift-loop PBR Medium: Modified M8 Carbon source: CO ₂ Temperature: 25°C Light: from 63 to 245 μmol/m ² /s, continuous light	nd	0.75	12

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

10.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
nd	nd	2.4 mg/g astaxanthin ¹⁰⁸ 1.3 mg/g canthaxanthin 0.8 mg/g ketolutein	335 mg/g TAGs ¹⁰⁸

10.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- ☼ **Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *C. zofingiensis* CCAP 211/14, 211/51, 221/2
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom

- ☼ **Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *C. zofingiensis* BEA 0468B, 0496B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

11. *Cryptothecodinium cohnii*

A heterotrophic non-photosynthetic species of dinoflagellate microalgae industrially used in the production of docosahexaenoic acid. DHA fraction can reach 30-50% of the total lipid content ¹⁰⁹.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
ATCC 30555, ATCC 30556, ATCC 30772.

11.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
ATCC 30555 ¹⁰⁹	System: 1 L fermenters Medium: optimized experimental medium Temperature: 27°C	nd	nd	25.3
ATCC 30556 ¹¹⁰	System: 250-ml Erlenmeyer flask and 5-L laboratory bioreactors Medium: standard medium (9 g/L glucose, 2 g/L yeast extract, 27.8 g/L sea salt) Temperature: 25°C Light: dark conditions	nd	nd	42 (under combined stress cultivation of temperature and nitrogen depletion)
M-1-2 ¹¹¹ (a mutant of <i>C. cohnii</i> ATCC 30556)	System: 5-L fermenter Medium: basal medium (25 g/L sea salt, 2 g/L yeast extract, 5-45 g/L glucose) Temperature: 25°C Light: dark conditions	nd	nd	45.17±0.71 (15-27 g/L glucose) 45.84±0.52 (80% medium replacement ratio)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

11.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
8-16% protein ¹⁰⁹ 22-28% lipid 40-60% starch	nd	nd	22:6(n-3) DHA 36-41% ¹⁰⁹ --- 22:6(n-3) DHA 20% ^e --- C12:0 3.08-3.88% ^f C14:0 12.82-14.28% C16:0 18.77-20.25% C18:0 2.19-3.43% C18:1 11.40-12.18% 22:6(n-3) 48.53-49.12%

11.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

-
Name: [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *C. cohnii* P10-012 (not distributed)
Location: Roscoff, France

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12. *Desmodesmus subspicatus*

Formerly known as *Scenedesmus subspicatus* (Chodat) ²⁶. A eukaryotic freshwater Chlorophyceae strain with applications for animal feed, nutritional supplement, and biofuel. It can be cultivated autotrophically, mixotrophically or heterotrophically ¹¹².

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 276/20

12.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 276/20 ²	System: PBR Medium: Jaworski's medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 μmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	0.09	0.11	2.1
CCAP 276/20 ¹¹³	System: 250 mL flasks (200 mL working volume) Medium: Jaworski's medium (different P levels) Temperature: 25°C Light: 144.8 μmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	nd	nd	2.4x10 ⁶ cells mL ⁻¹ (in low-P medium) 5.2x10 ⁶ cells mL ⁻¹ (in intermediate-P medium) 4.6x10 ⁶ cells mL ⁻¹ (in high-P medium)
nd ¹¹⁴ <i>Isolated from the River Nile, Egypt</i>	System: 1 L flasks (700 mL working volume) Medium: BBM Temperature: 28±2°C Light: 2500 lux, L:D cycle nd	nd	~0.9 (stationary phase) ~0.65 (late exponential phase)	nd

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

12.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
58% protein ² 16% lipid 29% carbohydrate	nd	19.6 mg/g total chlorophyll ² 0.3 mg/g total carotenoid --- 0.098±0.061 pg cell ⁻¹ Chlorophyll-a (<i>in Low N medium</i>) ¹¹⁵ 0.617±0.111 pg cell ⁻¹ Chlorophyll-a (<i>in High N medium</i>) ¹¹⁵	C14:0 1.5% ² C16:0 21.8% C16:1 6.0% C16:2 4.0% C16:3 0.7% C18:1 17.9% C18:2 21.7% C18:3 3.8% other 22.6%

12.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- ☉ **Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Desmodesmus* sp. (various), *D. subspicatus* BEA 0750B, 0141B, 0141/1, 0141/2, 0561, 0530B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

- ☉ **Name:** [Algal Research Group, Swansea University](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.
Expertise: bioenergy, biotechnology, chemistry, ecophysiology, engineering, large-scale development, mathematical models, molecular biology. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Scenedesmus subspicatus* ⁶⁴, *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* ^{61, 65}, *Dunaliella salina* ⁶⁵, *Micractinium inermum* ⁶⁵, *Porphyridium purpureum* ^{62, 63}

Location: Swansea, UK

- ☉ **Name:** [Department of Chemical and Biological Engineering, The University of Sheffield](#)
Network: [Algal Biotechnology Sheffield Network](#)
Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.
Expertise: Research outputs with microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Scenedesmus subspicatus* ⁶⁴, *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* ^{61, 65}, *Dunaliella salina* ⁶⁵⁻⁶⁷, *Micractinium inermum* ⁶⁵, *Chlorella vulgaris* ^{68, 69}, *Phaeodactylum tricornerutum* ^{70, 71}, *Nannochloropsis salina* ⁶⁶, *Nannochloropsis oceanica* ⁷¹

Location: Sheffield, UK

⊗ **Name:** [Spanish Society of Microalgae and Subproducts](#) (SEMS)

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development

Expertise: biotechnology, chemistry, marketing and valorisation. The company offers various laboratory services and products for agriculture, with various microalgae being produced on a continuous basis ¹¹⁶:

- *Arthrospira platensis*, *Nannochloropsis gaditana*, *Scenedesmus* sp., and ***Scenedesmus subspicatus***

Locations: Rota, Spain

13. *Dunaliella salina*

A eukaryotic marine Chlorophyceae strain that is extremely salt-tolerant and is widely cultivated as a source of beta-carotene. It has commercial interest as a source of anti-oxidant, colouring, nutritional supplement and cosmetics ^{117–120}. Large scale cultivation of *D. salina* is typically in open pond or large coastal lagoons ¹²¹.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 19/18

13.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 19/18 ²	System: PBR Medium: F2 (f/2) medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 70 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 16h L: 8h D	0.135	0.224	1.28
CCAP 19/18 ¹²²	System: PBR Medium: sterilised seawater Temperature: 21°C Light: 300 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ (blue light, red light) 12h L: 12h D	nd	nd	~1.0 (red light) ~0.7 (blue light)
nd ¹²³ <i>obtained from NLP corp (Busan, Korea)</i>	System: PBR (5L, 3 L working volume) Medium: f/2 medium Temperature: 20°C Light: 108.9 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 12h L: 12h D	nd	0.0375	0.25
nd ¹²⁴ <i>obtained from Guangyu Co. (Shanghai, China)</i>	System: Bubble column (350 mL working volume) Medium: high-salinity medium Temperature: 28°C Light: 100, 800 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, Continuous	0.66	nd	3.38 (at 800 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$) ~0.5 (at 100 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

13.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
48% protein ² 24% lipid 23% carbohydrate ---	41% C ² 2% N C/N ratio 21	27 mg/g beta-carotene ²	C16:0 28.1% ² C16:1 2.0% C18:0 2.9% C18:1 17.2% C18:2 9.2% C18:3 15.9% C20:1 4.8% other 19.9%
57% protein ⁶ 6% lipid 32% carbohydrate ---			
~42% lipids in two-stage system ⁴⁹			

13.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- ⊗ **Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *D. salina* 19/12, 19/18, 19/20, 19/25, 19/31, *Dunaliella* sp.
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- ⊗ **Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *D. salina* IFDSAL-JY215, IFDSAL-DIOX, DSALGB1, DSALGC3
Location: Roscoff, France
- ⊗ **Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *D. salina* BEA 0001, BEA 0162B, 0165B,
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain
- ⊗ **Name:** [A4F – Algae 4 Future](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated partner
Business/organisation type: bio-bank, producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Their microalgae track-production (large and pilot scale) includes ¹⁷:
 - *Arthrospira platensis*, *Chlamydomonas* sp., *Chlorella vulgaris*, ***Dunaliella salina***, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Lobosphaera incisa*, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*, *Phaeodactylum tricorutum*, *Prorocentrum cassubicum*, *Raphidonema* sp.,

Scenedesmus sp., *Scotiellopsis* sp., *Synechococcus* sp., *Synechocystis* sp., *Tetraselmis* sp.,
Thalassiosira weissflogii, *Tisochrysis lutea*

Location: Lisbon, Portugal

- ⊗ **Name:** [Algal Research Group, Swansea University](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.

Expertise: bioenergy, biotechnology, chemistry, ecophysiology, engineering, large-scale development, mathematical models, molecular biology. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Scenedesmus subspicatus*⁶⁴, *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*^{61,65}, *Dunaliella salina*⁶⁵,
*Micractinum inermum*⁶⁵, *Porphyridium purpureum*^{62,63}

Location: Swansea, UK

- ⊗ **Name:** [Algalimento](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated partner

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Algalimento currently produces all-year round high-quality biomass of¹²⁵:

- *Tetraselmis* sp., *Spirulina canariensis*, *Dunaliella salina*

Locations: Lisbon, Portugal

- ⊗ **Name:** [Department of Chemical and Biological Engineering, The University of Sheffield](#)

Network: [Algal Biotechnology Sheffield Network](#)

Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.

Expertise: Environment, biotechnology. Research outputs with microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Scenedesmus subspicatus*⁶⁴, *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*^{61,65}, *Dunaliella salina*⁶⁵⁻⁶⁷,
*Micractinum inermum*⁶⁵, *Chlorella vulgaris*^{68,69}, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*^{70,71},
*Nannochloropsis salina*⁶⁶, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*⁷¹

Location: Sheffield, UK

- ⊗ **Name:** [Group of Biotechnology and Aquaculture](#), Universidad de Santiago de Compostela

Business/organization type: research & development, higher education

Expertise: biotechnology, aquaculture. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- [*Dunaliella salina*, *Dunaliella tertiolecta*]¹²², *Haematococcus pluvialis*¹²⁶, [*Tetraselmis suecica*, *Tetraselmis* sp.]¹²⁷ *Rhodomonas lens*¹²⁸

Location: Santiago de Compostela, A Coruña, Spain

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- Name:** [IBVF - Instituto de Bioquímica Vegetal y Fotosíntesis, Microalgae Biotechnology Group](#)
Business/organisation type: research & development
Expertise: bioenergy, ecophysiology, molecular biology. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Anabaena* sp. ^{5,7}, *Porphyridium purpureum* ⁵, *Scenedesmus vacuolatus* ⁵, *Nostoc* ⁵, *Dunaliella salina* ⁸

Location: Sevilla, Spain

- Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: research and development
Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Alexandrium minutum* ⁴¹, *Alexandrium tamarense* ⁴¹, *Bigelowiella natans* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumillum* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros gracilis* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros minus* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros mulleri* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros* sp. *Tenuissimus* like ⁴¹, *Chlorella autotrophica* ⁴¹, *Chlorella vulgaris* ⁴¹, *Chloroarchonion reptans* ⁴¹, *Closterium baillyanum* ⁴¹, *Cyanophora paradoxa* ^{41,42}, *Cylindrotheca closterium* ⁴³, *Dunaliella salina* ^{41,44}, *Dunaliella* sp. ⁴¹, *Dunaliella tertiolecta* ^{41,45}, *Emiliania huxleyi* ⁴¹, *Haematococcus pluvialis* ⁴¹, *Heterocapsa triquetra* ⁴⁶, *Isochrysis galbana* ⁴¹, *Nitzschia* sp. ⁴¹, *Odontella aurita* ⁴¹, *Ostreococcus tauri* ⁴¹, *Phaeodactylum tricornerutum* ⁴¹, *Porphyridium purpureum* (*Porphyridium cruentum*) ^{44,47,48}, *Rhodella violacea* ⁴¹, *Rhodomonas salina* ^{41,49}, *Scenedesmus acutus* ⁴¹, *Scenedesmus obliquus* ⁴¹, *Skeletonema grethae* ⁴¹, *Tetraselmis suecica* ⁴¹, *Thalassiosira pseudonana* ⁴¹, *Tisochrysis lutea* ⁵⁰, *Euglena proxima* ⁴¹

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina* (*A. platensis*), from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

- Name:** [Microalgae group at Centro de Investigaciones Científicas Avanzadas \(CICA\), University of A Coruña](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae Partner
Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.
Expertise: chemistry, ecophysiology, genomics, monitoring. Research outputs involving microalgae at University of A Coruña include (but are not limited to):

 - *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* ⁷², *Dunaliella salina* ⁷³, *Haematococcus pluvialis* ⁷⁴

Location: A Coruña, Spain

- Name:** [NeoAlgae](#)
Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing

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Expertise: aquaculture, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. The company produces a wide range of **Spirulina**-based products for food, cosmetics, and agriculture ¹⁰². Their R&D division specialises on various extracts from ¹⁰³:

- *Dunaliella salina*, *Haematococcus pluviialis*, *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Isochrysis galbana*, *Nannochloropsis gaditana* ¹⁰³

Locations: Asturias, Spain

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14. *Dunaliella tertiolecta*

A eukaryotic brackish water Chlorophyceae strain that is less salt tolerant than *D. salina* and has lower productivity of beta-carotene but is of interest for its fatty acid yields with applications for nutritional supplements, and biofuel ¹²⁹.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 19/6B, BE 003

14.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 16/6B ²	System: PBR Medium: F2 (f/2) medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 μmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	0.048	0.128	1.6
CCAP 19/6B ¹²²	System: PBR Medium: sterilised seawater Temperature: 21°C Light: 300 μmol/m ² /s (blue light, red light) 12h L: 12h D	nd	nd	~1.2 (red light) ~0.8 (blue light)
nd ¹²³ <i>obtained from NLP corp (Busan, Korea)</i>	System: PBR (5L, 3 L working volume) Medium: f/2 medium Temperature: 20°C Light: 108.9 μmol/m ² /s, 12h L: 12h D	nd	0.0442	0.28

BE 003 ¹³⁰	System: PBR (2.2 L working volume) Medium: f/2 medium (modified with various NaNO ₃ concentrations) Temperature: 28°C Light: 17.5 klx continuous	nd	nd	0.45±0.02 (75 mg/L NaNO ₃) 1.27±0.07 (300 mg/L NaNO ₃)
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

14.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
58% protein ² 12% lipid 8% carbohydrate --- ~40% lipids in two-stage system ¹²³	44% C ² 2% N C/N ratio 20	3.95±0.06 to 5.1±0.4 mg/g total carotenoids ¹³⁰	C16:0 17.7% ² C16:1 0.9% C16:2 3.0% C16:3 1.2% C16:4 10.6% C18:1 4.9% C18:2 12.4% C18:3 30.2% other 19.1%

14.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

-
Name: [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *D. tertiolecta* AC148, *Dunaliella* sp. AC769
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France

-
Name: [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *D. tertiolecta* 19/22, 19/23, 19/24, 19/27, 19/42, 19/5, 19/6B, 19/7C
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom

-
Name: [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *D. tertiolecta* IFREMER (PLY83), *Dunaliella* sp.
Location: Roscoff, France

-
Name: [Spanish Algae Bank](#)

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Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *D. tertiolecta* BEA 0837B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

- ⊗ **Name:** [Group of Biotechnology and Aquaculture](#), Universidad de Santiago de Compostela
Business/organization type: research & development, higher education
Expertise: biotechnology, aquaculture. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - [*Dunaliella salina*, ***Dunaliella tertiolecta***]¹²², *Haematococcus pluvialis*¹²⁶, [*Tetraselmis suecica*, *Tetraselmis* sp.]¹²⁷ *Rhodomonas lens*¹³¹

Location: Santiago de Compostela, A Coruña, Spain

- ⊗ **Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: research and development
Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - *Alexandrium minutum*⁴¹, *Alexandrium tamarense*⁴¹, *Bigelowiella natans*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumillum*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros gracilis*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros minus*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros mulleri*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros* sp. *Tenuissimus* like⁴¹, *Chlorella autotrophica*⁴¹, *Chlorella vulgaris*⁴¹, *Chloroarchonion reptans*⁴¹, *Closterium baillyanum*⁴¹, *Cyanophora paradoxa*^{41,42}, *Cylindrotheca closterium*⁴³, *Dunaliella salina*^{41,44}, *Dunaliella* sp.⁴¹, ***Dunaliella tertiolecta***^{41,45}, *Emiliana huxleyi*⁴¹, *Haematococcus pluvialis*⁴¹, *Heterocapsa triquetra*⁴⁶, *Isochrysis galbana*⁴¹, *Nitzschia* sp.⁴¹, *Odontella aurita*⁴¹, *Ostreococcus tauri*⁴¹, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁴¹, *Porphyridium purpureum* (*Porphyridium cruentum*)^{44,47,48}, *Rhodella violacea*⁴¹, *Rhodomonas salina*^{41,49}, *Scenedesmus acutus*⁴¹, *Scenedesmus obliquus*⁴¹, *Skeletonema grethae*⁴¹, *Tetraselmis suecica*⁴¹, *Thalassiosira pseudonana*⁴¹, *Tisochrysis lutea*⁵⁰, *Euglena proxima*⁴¹

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina* (*A. platensis*), from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

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15. *Euglena gracilis*

A unicellular phototrophic freshwater microalga. It can grow under phototrophic, heterotrophic and mixotrophic conditions. *E. gracilis* synthesises relevant bioproducts at a commercial level such as protein containing essential amino acids, pro(vitamins), lipids, and the β -1,3-glucan paramylon¹³².

Commonly cultivated strains include:
NIES-48

15.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
NIES-48 ¹³³	<p>System: 2.5 L glass vessel bioreactors</p> <p>Medium: Chemically defined medium</p> <p>Carbon source: 1.8% CO₂ enriched air (for phototrophic growth); glucose (for mixotrophic and heterotrophic growth)</p> <p>Temperature: 23, 27, 30°C</p> <p>Light: 400 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ (for phototrophic growth) and dark conditions (for heterotrophic growth)</p>	nd	nd	<p>5 (in phototrophic cultures with high light and 23°C)</p> <p>10.5 (in mixotrophic cultures at 27°C)</p>
nd ¹³⁴ (obtained from the Culture Collection Centre of the Institute of Applied Microbiology, University of Tokyo, Japan)	<p>System: 500 mL erlenmeyer flasks and airlift photobioreactor</p> <p>Medium: BG11 medium and different NPKs</p> <p>Temperature: 25°C\pm1</p> <p>Light: 2570 Lux, L:D cycle: continuous light illumination</p>	nd	nd	<p>26.0 $\times 10^7$ cell/mL (in flasks)</p> <p>228.8 $\times 10^7$ cell/mL (in airlift PBR)</p>

NIES-48 ¹³⁵	System: 15 L polycarbonate culture vessel Medium: municipal wastewater Temperature: 28±1°C Light: 80 µmol/m ² /s, 16 L: 8 D cycle	nd	0.087 (in a co-culture with bacteria containing 8×10 ⁶ CFU/mL)	0.7
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

15.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
12-34% protein ¹³³ 22% lipid ---	nd	6 µg/mL chlorophyll a+b ^j (in co-culture with bacteria)	20:5(n-3) EPA 0.48% ¹³³ 22:6(n-3) DHA 0.38%
33.3% protein ¹³⁴ 16.4% lipid ---			
30.9% lipid ¹³⁵			

15.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

-
Name: [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *E. gracilis* CCAP 1224/38, 1224/5Y, 1224/5Z, *Euglena* sp. CCAP 1224/47
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom

-
Name: [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Euglena* sp. BEA 0201B, 0799, 0202B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

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16. *Galdieria sulphuraria*

A unicellular red microalga which grows efficiently in extreme environments with acidic conditions and high temperatures. *G. sulphuraria* produces a large amount of biomass and many beneficial compounds ¹³⁶.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
074 W, 064/309

16.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
074 W ¹³⁶	<p>System: 300 mL shaking flasks</p> <p>Medium: modified 2 Allen's medium</p> <p>Carbon source: glucose (for mixotrophic and heterotrophic growth)</p> <p>Temperature: 42°C</p> <p>Light: 50 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ continuous light (for phototrophic and mixotrophic growth), dark (for heterotrophic growth)</p>	nd	nd	3.8 \pm 0.2 (mixotrophic)
064/309 ¹³⁷	<p>System: 5 L glass cylindrical bioreactors</p> <p>Medium: Allen medium</p> <p>Carbon source: glycerol (for heterotrophic growth)</p> <p>Light: 150 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ (for phototrophic growth)</p> <p>L:D cycle nd</p>	nd	nd	5.7 (autotrophic) 29 (heterotrophic)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

16.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
26–32% protein ¹³⁷ 63–69% carbohydrate 11-18% lipid	nd	575 mg/kg astaxanthin ¹³⁷ 387 mg/kg lutein 12 mg/kg chlorophyll-a 4.5-79 g/kg allophycocyanin 0.2-0.5 g/kg phycocyanin 3.3-6.5 g/kg phycoerytrin	C14:0 0.9-2.7% ¹³⁷ C16:0 14.7-39.4% C16:1 2.4% C18:0 4.7% C18:1 8.6-57.5% C18:2 19.5-45.2% C18:3 1.1-2.7%

17. *Graesiella* sp.

A unicellular green microalga with broadly ellipsoidal or globose cells. This microalga presents high capacity of adaptation to a wide range of culture pH ¹³⁸.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
WBG-1, NC-M1

17.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
WBG-1 ¹³⁸	<p>System: bubbled column PBR, 10 L circular pond, 30 L tank PBR, 200 m² raceway pond</p> <p>Medium: modified BG11 medium</p> <p>Carbon source: 1% v/v CO₂</p> <p>Temperature: 30°C</p> <p>Light: 300 μmol/m²/s, L:D cycle nd</p>	nd	18.9 g/m ² /d (in 30L tank)	161.8 g/m ² (in 30L tank)
NC-M1 ¹³⁹	<p>System: 1 L Erlenmeyer flasks</p> <p>Medium: BG11 medium</p> <p>Temperature: 25°C</p> <p>Light: 50 μmol/m²/s, 16h L:8h D cycle</p>	nd	nd	1.2 (with 45.2 μM Fe)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

17.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
12-14% protein ¹³⁸ 32-40% carbohydrate 22-35% lipid (in 200 m ² raceway cultivation) --- 30-65% lipid ¹³⁹	nd	nd	C5-C14 5-10% ¹³⁸ C16-C18 70-75% C19-C24 7-10% --- C14:0 27.4-29.64% ¹³⁹ C16:0 0.83-5.49% C16:2 1.19-4.99% C18:1 27.43-47.04% C18:2 8.86-22.03% C20:2 6.72-13.52%

17.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

-
Name: [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *G. emersoni* CCAP 211/1A, 211/1M, 211/1N, 211/15, 211/55, 211/8G, 211/8H, 2118P
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom

-
Name: [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *G. vacuolata* BEA 0618B, 0615B, 0573B, 0616B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

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18. *Haematococcus pluvialis*

A eukaryotic freshwater Chlorophyceae strain with the ability to produce very high concentrations of astaxanthin, with applications for aquaculture, nutritional supplement, and cosmetics, and with antioxidant characteristics. *H. pluvialis* has a green phase then a red phase of growth, which is induced by light, nitrogen or saline stress ^{140_142}.

Commonly cultivated strains include:

CCAP 34/6, SCCAP K-0084, SCCAP K-0084, LUGU, CPCC 93

18.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 34/6 ²	System: PBR Medium: Jaworski's medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 µmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	0.098	0.157	3.14
SCCAP K-0084 ¹⁴³	System: 250 mL flasks Medium: BG11 medium Carbon source: ribose, sodium acetate, or gluconate Temperature: 25°C Light: 45±3 µmol/m ² /s, L:D cycle nd	nd	nd	1.03 (on ribose) 0.77 (on acetate) 1.12 (on gluconate)
SCCAP K-0084 ¹⁴³	System: 250 mL flasks Medium: BG11 medium Carbon source: gluconate Temperature: 25°C Light: 105±3 µmol/m ² /s, L:D cycle nd	nd	nd	2.09
LUGU ¹⁴⁴ (18S GenBankKM115647.1)	System: 1 L flask (650 mL working volume). Medium: BG11 medium + fulvic acid	nd	nd	1.57 (with 0 mg/L fulvic acid) 1.84

	Carbon source: sodium acetate Temperature: 25°C Light: 50 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ L:D cycle nd			(with 5 mg/L fulvic acid)
CPCC 93 ¹⁴⁵	System: 2.2 L PBR Medium: M1B5 Temperature: 23±2°C Light: 15-30 klx 12 h L: 12h D	nd	nd	2.028±0.09 (on air) 4.37±0.07 (on 5% CO ₂)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

18.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
68% protein ² 26% lipid 9% carbohydrate	36% C ² 4% N C/N ratio 10 --- 43.57±0.61% C ¹⁴⁵ 6.26±0.54% H 1.98±0.16% N 0.47±0.03% S	23.2 mg/g astaxanthin ² 2.8 mg/g beta-carotene 10.2 mg/g lutein 5.8 mg/g total chlorophyll (in red phase) --- 5.2±1.7 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ chlorophyll ¹⁴³ (at 0 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$) 41.3±2.9 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ chlorophyll (at 105 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$) --- 5.01 mg/g astaxanthin content ¹⁴⁴	C16:0 22.4% ² C16:1 0.6% C16:2 2.1% C16:3 3.1% C16:4 5.8% C18:0 0.9% C18:1 19.5% C18:2 28.7% C18:3 12.6% other 4.3%

18.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

-
Name: [AlgoBank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *H. pluvialis* AC136, 143, 587, 588
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France

-
Name: [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *H. pluvialis* BEA 1360B

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Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

⊗ **Name:** [A4F – Algae 4 Future](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: bio-bank, producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Their microalgae track-production (large and pilot scale) includes ¹⁷:

- *Arthrospira platensis*, *Chlamydomonas* sp., *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Dunaliella salina*, ***Haematococcus pluvialis***, *Lobosphaera incisa*, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*, *Phaeodactylum tricorutum*, *Prorocentrum cassubicum*, *Raphidonema* sp., *Scenedesmus* sp., *Scotiellopsis* sp., *Synechococcus* sp., *Synechocystis* sp., *Tetraselmis* sp., *Thalassiosira weissflogii*, *Tisochrysis lutea*

Locations: Lisbon, Portugal

⊗ **Name:** [Aqualgae](#)

Business/organisation: research and development

Expertise: design and installation of high-productivity photobioreactors, suppliers of culturing media, inoculums, and lyophilised cultures of ²⁰:

- *Chlorella*, ***Haematococcus***, *Arthrospira*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*, *Pavlova*, *Chaetoceros*, *Skeletonema*, *Nitzschia*, *Rhodomonas*, *Nannochloropsis*

Locations: Diana do Castelo, Portugal; and A Coruña, Spain

⊗ **Name:** [Group of Biotechnology and Aquaculture](#), Universidad de Santiago de Compostela

Business/organization type: research & development, higher education

Expertise: biotechnology, aquaculture. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- [*Dunaliella salina*, *Dunaliella tertiolecta*] ¹²², ***Haematococcus pluvialis*** ¹²⁶, [*Tetraselmis suecica*, *Tetraselmis* sp.] ¹²⁷ *Rhodomonas lens* ¹³¹

Location: Santiago de Compostela, A Coruña, Spain

⊗ **Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Alexandrium minutum* ⁴¹, *Alexandrium tamarense* ⁴¹, *Bigelowiella natans* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumillum* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros gracilis* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros minus* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros mulleri* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros* sp. *Tenuissimus* like ⁴¹, *Chlorella autotrophica* ⁴¹, *Chlorella vulgaris* ⁴¹, *Chloroarchnion reptans* ⁴¹, *Closterium*

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*baillyanum*⁴¹, *Cyanophora paradoxa*^{41,42}, *Cylindrotheca closterium*⁴³, *Dunaliella salina*^{41,44}, *Dunaliella* sp.⁴¹, *Dunaliella tertiolecta*^{41,45}, *Emiliana huxleyi*⁴¹, ***Haematococcus pluvialis***⁴¹, *Heterocapsa triquetra*⁴⁶, *Isochrysis galbana*⁴¹, *Nitzschia* sp.⁴¹, *Odontella aurita*⁴¹, *Ostreococcus tauri*⁴¹, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁴¹, *Porphyridium purpureum* (*Porphyridium cruentum*)^{44,47,48}, *Rhodella violacea*⁴¹, *Rhodomonas salina*^{41,49}, *Scenedesmus acutus*⁴¹, *Scenedesmus obliquus*⁴¹, *Skeletonema grethae*⁴¹, *Tetraselmis suecica*⁴¹, *Thalassiosira pseudonana*⁴¹, *Tisochrysis lutea*⁵⁰, *Euglena proxima*⁴¹

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina* (*A. platensis*), from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

- ⊗ **Name:** [Microalgae group at Centro de Investigaciones Científicas Avanzadas \(CICA\), University of A Coruña](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Partner

Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.

Expertise: chemistry, ecophysiology, genomics, monitoring. Research outputs involving microalgae at University of A Coruña include (but are not limited to):

- *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*⁷², *Dunaliella salina*⁷³, ***Haematococcus pluvialis***⁷⁴

Location: A Coruña, Spain

- ⊗ **Name:** [NeoAlgae](#)

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: aquaculture, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. The company produces a wide range of **Spirulina**-based products for food, cosmetics, and agriculture¹⁰². Their R&D division specialises on various extracts from¹⁰³:

- *Dunaliella salina*, ***Haematococcus pluvialis***, *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Isochrysis galbana*, *Nannochloropsis gaditana*¹⁰³

Locations: Asturias, Spain

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19. *Isochrysis galbana*

A eukaryotic marine microalga which is a species of Haptophyta. For its good nutritive characteristics (especially in relation to polyunsaturated fatty-acid composition), is of substantial interest in aquaculture ¹⁴⁶. It is also investigated for its high amount of fucoxanthin ¹⁴⁷.

19.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
nd ¹⁴⁸ <i>from Marine Microalgae Research Center, Ocean University of China</i>	System: Erlenmeyer flasks Medium: f/2 Temperature: 23°C Light: 4.0 mW/cm ² , 16 h L: 8 h D	nd	nd	1.69x10 ⁷ cells/mL (500 μmol/L phosphorous)
nd ¹⁴⁹ <i>Aquatic Research Laboratory at Isfahan University of Technology, Isfahan, Iran</i>	System: 10 L carboys Medium: Walne's medium Temperature: 25°C Light: 80 mmol photons/m ² /s, 12 h L: 12 h D	nd	nd	1.55x10 ⁷ cells/mL (144mg/L nitrogen)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

19.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
30% protein ¹⁴⁸ 33% carbohydrate (100 µmol/L phosphorous) ---	nd	3.24% chlorophyll ¹⁴⁸ (100 µmol/L phosphorous) ---	C14:0 26.34% ¹⁴⁹ C16:0 43.46% C16:1 1.4% C18:1n-7 17.25% C18:3n-3 3.52%
36.3% protein ¹⁴⁹ (36 mg/L nitrogen) 47% carbohydrate (0 mg/L nitrogen) 30.6% lipids (144 mg/L nitrogen)		1.21 mg/L total carotenoid ¹⁴⁹ (72 mg/L nitrogen)	C20:0 4.42% C20:3n-3 2.03% (0 mg/L nitrogen)

19.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- ☼ **Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *I. galbana* CCAP 927/1, 927/20, 941/3, 949/1
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- ☼ **Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *I. galbana* AC101 (not distributed), AC34, AC80, PLY240, PLY507, PLY8, GE_FL_IC_SingleCell_103, GE_FL_IC_SingleCell_104, GE_DV_IC_DIL_194
Location: Roscoff, France
- ☼ **Name:** [AlgoSource](#)
Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: engineering, large-scale development, industrial ecology. Know-how on *Spirulina* and its principal ingredient phycocyanin. The company is also working on extracting molecules of interest from other microalgae ¹⁰⁰:
 - *Spirulina, Chlorella, Scenedesmus, Tetraselmis, Isochrysis*
Locations: Saint-Nazaire, France
- ☼ **Name:** [ANFACO-CECOPESCA](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae project Lead Coordinator

Business/organisation type: Marketing, research & development and innovation support in food and marine technology.

Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology, marketing, valorisation and functionality of microalgal compounds. Microalgal expertise includes (not limited to) ^{39,40}:

- *Chaetoceros calcitrans*, *C. salsugineus*, *Conticribra weissflogii* (synonym of *Thalassiosira weissflogii*), ***Isochrysis galbana***, *Nannochloropsis gaditana*, *Pavlova gyrams*, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Rhodomonas lens*, *Tetraselmis chuii*, *Tisochrysis lutea*

ANFACO-CECOPECA offers production of tailor-made microalgal biomass. Read more in the [EnhanceMicroAlgae marketplace](#).

Location: Vigo, Spain

⊗ **Name:** [Algal Research Group, Swansea University](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.

Expertise: Microalgae biotechnology, biomass characterization, upstream and downstream process, chemistry, ecophysiology, engineering, large-scale development, molecular biology. Research expertise with microalgae includes (but is not limited to):

- *Scenedesmus obliquus* and *Chlorella vulgaris* ⁵⁸, *Arthrospira maxima* ⁵⁹, *Nannochloropsis* spp. ⁶⁰, *Micractinum inermum* ⁶¹, *Porphyridium purpureum* ^{62,63}, *Nosctoc* sp., ***Isochrysis galbana*** and over 25 common microalgae species including green algae, diatoms, cyanobacteria and dinoflagellates.

Location: Swansea, UK

⊗ **Name:** [Aqualgae](#)

Business/organisation: research and development

Expertise: design and installation of high-productivity photobioreactors, suppliers of culturing media, inoculums, and lyophilised cultures of ²⁰:

- *Chlorella*, *Haematococcus*, *Arthrospira*, *Tetraselmis*, ***Isochrysis***, *Pavlova*, *Chaetoceros*, *Skeletonema*, *Nitzschia*, *Rhodomonas*, *Nannochloropsis*

Locations: Diana do Castelo, Portugal; and A Coruña, Spain

⊗ **Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Alexandrium minutum* ⁴¹, *Alexandrium tamarense* ⁴¹, *Bigelowiella natans* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumillum* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros gracilis* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros minus* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros mulleri* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros* sp. *Tenuissimus* like ⁴¹, *Chlorella autotrophica* ⁴¹, *Chlorella vulgaris* ⁴¹, *Chloroarchnion reptans* ⁴¹, *Closterium baillyanum* ⁴¹, *Cyanophora paradoxa* ^{41,42}, *Cylindrotheca closterium* ⁴³, *Dunaliella salina* ^{41,44}, *Dunaliella* sp. ⁴¹, *Dunaliella tertiolecta* ^{41,45}, *Emiliania huxleyi* ⁴¹, *Haematococcus*

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*pluvialis*⁴¹, *Heterocapsa triquetra*⁴⁶, ***Isochrysis galbana***⁴¹, *Nitzschia* sp.⁴¹, *Odontella aurita*⁴¹, *Ostreococcus tauri*⁴¹, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁴¹, *Porphyridium purpureum* (*Porphyridium cruentum*)^{44, 47, 48}, *Rhodella violacea*⁴¹, *Rhodomonas salina*^{41, 49}, *Scenedesmus acutus*⁴¹, *Scenedesmus obliquus*⁴¹, *Skeletonema grethae*⁴¹, *Tetraselmis suecica*⁴¹, *Thalassiosira pseudonana*⁴¹, *Tisochrysis lutea*⁵⁰, *Euglena proxima*⁴¹

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina* (*A. platensis*), from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

☼ **Name:** [NeoAlgae](#)

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: aquaculture, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. The company produces a wide range of **Spirulina**-based products for food, cosmetics, and agriculture¹⁰². Their R&D division specialises on various extracts from¹⁰³:

- *Dunaliella salina*, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Chlorella vulgaris*, ***Isochrysis galbana***, *Nannochloropsis gaditana*¹⁰³

Locations: Asturias, Spain

☼ **Name:** [PhytoBloom](#)/Necton

Business/organisation: producer, research and development

Expertise: aquaculture, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. Their line of products include culture media for microalgae, and aquaculture food concentrates from¹⁵⁰:

- *Nannochloropsis*, *Tetraselmis*, ***Isochrysis***, and *Phaeodactylum*

Location: Olhão and Algarve, Portugal

☼ **Name:** [Xanthella Ltd.](#)

Business/organisation: research and development

Expertise: Design and test bespoke PBRs, consultancy, repair and recycling of old systems, active research and development. The company has worked on:

- *Chaetoceros muelleri*, *Chlamydomonas acidophila*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Dunaliella primolecta*, *Desmodesmus subspicatus*, *Fragilaria* sp., ***Isochrysis galbana***, *Limnoraphis robusta*, *Nannochloropsis* sp., *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Porphyridium cruentum*, *Synechocystis* sp., *T-isochrysis lutea*

Location: European Marine Science Park, Argyl, Scotland

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20. *Jaagichlorella luteoviridis*

Formerly known as *Chlorella luteoviridis* (Chodat) ¹⁵¹. A eukaryotic freshwater Trebouxiophyceae strain (also known as *Heterochlorella luteoviridis* or *Jaagichlorella luteoviridis*) with fast growth rate and along with other *Chlorella* sp. has applications for animal feed, nutritional supplement, and biofuel. It can be cultivated autotrophically, mixotrophically or heterotrophically. ¹⁵²

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 211/3, CCAP 211/4, CCAP 211/5B

20.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 211/3 ²	System: PBR Medium: Jaworski's medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 μmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	0.29	0.36	2.52
Indigenous wastewater <i>C. luteoviridis</i> strain ¹⁵³	System: 250 mL conical flasks (batch; semi-continuous) Medium: Raw municipal wastewater secondary treated effluent (RMWSE) + 25 % v/v sludge liquor Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 μmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	nd	~0.8 (batch) 1.78 (semi-continuous)	0.84 (batch) 6.01-7.99 (semi-continuous)
Indigenous wastewater <i>C. luteoviridis</i> strain ¹⁵³	System: Open pond (150 L, 10 cm depth) Medium: RMWSE + 25 % v/v/ sludge liquor Temperature: outdoors Light: outdoors	nd	~0.31 (in summer) ~0.25 (in spring)	nd

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

20.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
47% protein ² 22% lipid 12% carbohydrate	nd	29.8 mg/g total chlorophyll ² 3.4 mg/g total carotenoid	C14:0 2.4% ² C16:0 25.0% C16:1 9.3% C18:0 7.2% C18:1 21.3% C18:2 9.7% C18:3 24.9% other 0.2%

20.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

-
Name: [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *J. luteoviridis* CCAP 211/10A, 211/10C, 211/10E, 211/3, 211/4, 211/5B
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom

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21. *Lyngbya lutea*

Formerly known as *Oscillatoria lutea* (C.Agardh) ²⁶. A cyanobacteria strain that has interest as a source of chemicals including butylated hydroxytoluene, which has antioxidant characteristics ¹⁵⁴.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 1459/3

21.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 1459/3 ²	System: PBR Medium: BG11 medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 16h L: 8h D	0.04	0.05	0.76
nd ¹⁵⁵ (<i>Oscillatoria lutea</i> var. <i>contorta</i>) obtained from the collection of the University of Texas	System: 500 mL flasks (250 mL working volume) Medium: grown on barley straw extract Temperature: 20°C Light: 65 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 12h L: 12h D	nd	nd	~600 $\mu\text{g L}$ (measured as <i>Chlorophyll a</i>)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

21.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigments	Fatty acids
48% protein ² 9% lipid 18% carbohydrate	nd	9.8 mg/g chlorophyll ² 1.7 mg/g carotenoids	nd

21.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

☼ **Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)

Business/organisation type: bio-bank

Strain(s) available: *Lyngbya* sp. CCAP 1446/10, 1446/7, 1473/2, 1473/4, *Oscillatoria lutea* var. *contorta* CCAP 1459/3, *Oscillatoria* sp. CCAP 1459/13

Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom

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22. *Microchloropsis salina*

Formerly known as *Nannochloropsis salina*²⁶. It is a marine microalga widely used in aquaculture as it is rich in PUFA (particularly EPA), antioxidant pigment, and numerous bioactive compounds¹⁵⁶.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
SAG 40.85, CCMP 1776.

22.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
nd ¹⁵⁶ <i>obtained from the culture collection of Cochin University of Science and Technology, India</i>	System: 250 mL conical flasks Medium: f/2 medium prepared in artificial seawater Temperature: 28±2°C Light: 27.02 μmol/m ² /s, L: D cycle nd	nd	nd	9.0x10 ⁶ cells/mL
SAG 40.85 ¹⁵⁷	System: 4 m ² (40 L) open thin-layer cascade reactor Medium: ASW medium Temperature and light: simulated conditions of Almería	nd	nd	15.4
nd ¹⁵⁸ <i>obtained from the Rajiv Gandhi Centre for Aquaculture, Marine Products Export Development Authority (MPEDA), Sirkali, Tamil Nadu, India</i>	System: Erlenmeyer flasks Medium: Walne medium Carbon source: glucose and sodium acetate (0.25, 0.5 and 1 g/L) Temperature: 27 °C Light: 3000 lux	nd	nd	1.795

22.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
~20% protein ¹⁵⁶ ~15% lipid ~10% carbohydrate --- 48% protein ¹⁵⁷ 16% lipid 26% carbohydrate <i>(in nutrient replete medium)</i> 12% protein 46% lipid 35% carbohydrate <i>(in nitrogen-limited medium)</i> --- 45% lipid ¹⁵⁸ <i>(in heterotrophic conditions)</i>	nd	~800 µg/L chlorophyll ¹⁵⁶ ~850 µg/L total carotenoids	C14:0 6.5% ¹⁵⁷ C16:0 22.0% C16:1 31.3% C18:0 0.4% C18:1 4.8% C18:1 0.4% C18:2 1.6% C18:3 0.1% C20:0 0.1% C20:1 0.1% C20:2 0.1% C20:4 4.0% C20:3 0.1% C20:5 28.3% <i>(in nutrient replete medium)</i> C14:0 3.4% C16:0 48.6% C16:1 30.1% C18:0 1.2 % C18:1 6.6 % C18:1 0.4 % C18:2 1.3 % C18:3 0.4 % C20:0 0.1 % C20:1 0.1 % C20:2 0.1 % C20:4 2.1 % C20:3 0.1 % C20:5 5.5 % <i>(in nitrogen-limited medium)</i>

22.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

-
Name: [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *M. salina* CCAP 849/2, 849/3, 849/4
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom

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- ⊗ **Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *M. salina* CCMP527
Location: Roscoff, France

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23. *Microcystis aeruginosa*

A cyanobacteria strain known for toxic bloom formation. It can produce neurotoxins and is also a source of butylated hydroxytoluene, which has antioxidant characteristics ¹⁵⁹.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 1450/1, FACHB-469.

23.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 1450/1 ²	System: PBR Medium: BG11 medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 μmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	0.04	0.06	0.68
FACHB-469 ¹⁶⁰	System: 250 mL flasks (150 mL working volume) Medium: BG11 medium with dissolved organic carbon, DOM Temperature: 25°C Light: 50 μmol/m ² /s, 12h L: 12h D	nd	nd	1.7x10 ⁷ cells/mL

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

23.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
66% protein ² 9% lipid 8% carbohydrate --- ~4.5-8 pg cell ⁻¹ protein ¹⁶⁰ ~2-12 pg cell ⁻¹ polysaccharides (under various organic sources)	nd	~0.4-0.55 ug 10 ⁶ cell ⁻¹ chlorophyll content ¹⁶¹	nd

23.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- ☼ **Name:** [Laboratoire Phycotoxines IFREMER](#)

Business/organisation: research and development, environmental monitoring

Expertise: chemistry, ecophysiology, molecular biology. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Tisochrysis lutea* ¹⁶², *Microcystis aeruginosa* ¹⁶³

The research team at IFREMER works in close collaboration with the EnhanceMicroAlgae team at [LIENSs, University of La Rochelle](#), France.

Location: Nantes, France

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24. *Nannochloropsis oculata*

A eukaryotic marine strain of the Eustigmatophyceae class with applications for nutritional supplement, and biofuel, particularly due to its fatty acid characteristics. It can be cultivated autotrophically in photobioreactor or open pond conditions, with a stress induction such as nitrogen starvation, typically used to induce higher fatty acid yields^{164, 165}.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 849/1

24.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 849/1 ²	System: PBR Medium: F2 (f/2) medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 16h L: 8h D	0.09	0.32	2.5
nd ¹²³ <i>obtained from NLP corp (Busan, Korea)</i>	System: PBR (5L, 3 L working volume) Medium: f/2 medium Temperature: 20°C Light: 108.9 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 12h L: 12h D	nd	0.0475	0.51
nd ¹⁶⁶ <i>obtained from the Fisheries Research Institute (Pingtung, Taiwan)</i>	System: 3 L PBR Two stages: 1 st N replete, 2 nd N deplete Medium: Basal medium with 35 g/L salinity Temperature: 25°C Light: 300, 500 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, Continuous	nd	nd	3.36 (at 300 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$) 3.44 (at 500 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

24.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
40% protein ² 33% lipid 10% carbohydrate --- ~30% lipids in two-stage system ¹²³ --- 43.2% lipid ¹⁶⁶ (at 300 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$) 44.5% lipid (at 500 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$)	55% C ² 3% N C/N ratio 21	nd	C14:0 7.2% ² C16:0 23.4% C16:1 26.9% C16:3 0.5% C18:1 13.2% C18:2 1.2% C20:4 2.7% C20:5 14.3% other 10.1% --- C14:0 4.13% ⁹⁹ C16:0 20.70% C16:1 17.12% C16:2 3.88% C16:3 5.35% C18:0 0.98% C18:1 7.46% C18:2 8.75% C18:3 10.08% C20:4 2.88% C20:5 18.67% $\Sigma\text{SFA}=25.8$ $\Sigma\text{MUFA}=24.58$ $\Sigma\text{PUFA}=49.62$ --- $\Sigma\text{SFA}=34.15\text{-}40.15\%$ ¹⁶⁶ $\Sigma\text{PUFA}=29.96\text{-}44.54\%$

24.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- ☉ **Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *N. oculata* AC225, ACAC227
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France

- ☉ **Name:** [Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa CCAP](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *N. oculata* CCAP 849/1, CCAP 849/7
Location: Scottish Marine institute, Scotland, UK

⊗ **Name:** [Algal Research Group, Swansea University](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.

Expertise: Microalgae biotechnology, biomass characterization, upstream and downstream process, chemistry, ecophysiology, engineering, large-scale development, molecular biology.

Research expertise with microalgae includes (but is not limited to):

- *Scenedesmus obliquus* and *Chlorella vulgaris*⁵⁸, *Arthrospira maxima*⁵⁹, ***Nannochloropsis* spp.**⁶⁰, *Micractinum inermum*⁶¹, *Porphyridium purpureum*^{62,63}, *Nostoc sp.*, *Isochrysis galbana* and over 25 common microalgae species including green algae, diatoms, cyanobacteria and dinoflagellates.

Location: Swansea, UK

⊗ **Name:** [Aqualgae](#)

Business/organisation: research and development

Expertise: design and installation of high-productivity photobioreactors, suppliers of culturing media, inoculums, and lyophilised cultures of²⁰:

- *Chlorella*, *Haematococcus*, *Arthrospira*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*, *Pavlova*, *Chaetoceros*, *Skeletonema*, *Nitzschia*, *Rhodomonas*, ***Nannochloropsis***

Locations: Diana do Castelo, Portugal; and A Coruña, Spain

⊗ **Name:** [Buggypower](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated partner

Business/organization type: producer, research & development, downstream processing

Expertise: feed, food, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. The company specialises in¹⁰¹:

- *Chlorella*, ***Nannochloropsis***, *Rhodomonas*

Location: Lisbon, Portugal (shared services centre & Alguimya store); Funchal, Portugal (Financial office); Porto Santo, Portugal (Buggypower production unit in partnership with Electricity Company of Madeira); San Pedro del Pinatar, Spain (Financial office); Lorqui, Spain (Research and development pilot plant)

⊗ **Name:** [Laboratoire GENie des Procédés Environnement – Agroalimentaire, GEPEA](#)

Business/organisation: research and development, higher education

Expertise: bioenergy, biotechnology, chemistry, engineering. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Chlorella vulgaris*⁹⁰, *Chlorella sorokiniana*⁹¹, *Parachlorella kessleri*⁹², ***Nannochloropsis oculata***⁹⁰

Location: Saint-Nazaire, France

⊗ **Name:** [PhytoBloom](#)/Necton

Business/organisation: producer, research and development

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Expertise: aquaculture, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. Their line of products include culture media for microalgae, and aquaculture food concentrates from ¹⁶⁷:

- ***Nannochloropsis***, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*, and *Phaeodactylum*

Location: Olhão and Algarve, Portugal

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25. *Nostoc* sp.

A cyanobacteria strain that is grown as a food and feed source, and a nutritional supplement in Asia due to its protein and vitamin constituents ¹⁶⁸.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 1403/17, TISTR 8872, TISTR 8873

25.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 1403/17 ²	System: PBR Medium: BG11 medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 70 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 16h L: 8h D	0.122	0.197	1.38
TISTR 8872 ¹⁶⁹	System: Conical flasks (300 mL working volume) Medium: BG11 medium Temperature: 28 \pm 1°C Light: 60 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 12h L: 12h D	nd	nd	0.3 \pm 0.0
TISTR 8873 ¹⁶⁹	System: Conical flasks (300 mL working volume) Medium: BG11 medium Temperature: 28 \pm 1°C Light: 60 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 12h L: 12h D	nd	nd	0.2 \pm 0.04

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

25.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
42% protein ² 8% lipid 33% carbohydrate --- From 30.66±0.58 to 32.85±1.52% starch ¹⁶⁹	nd	0.6 mg/g chlorophyll ² 1.7 mg/g carotenoids	nd

25.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- **Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Nostoc commune* AC661
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France

- **Name:** [Blue Biotechnology and Ecotoxicology Culture Collection \(LEGE\) at CIIMAR](#)
CIIMAR is an EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Nostoc* sp. LEGE 06158, 06077, 07365, 13413, 12447, 12448, 12449, 12450, 12451, 12453, 12454, 12456,
 Read more about the services offered by the LEGE culture collection in the [EnhanceMicroAlgae marketplace](#).
Location: Porto, Portugal

- **Name:** [Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa CCAP](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Nostoc* sp. CCAP 1403/17, 1453/25, 1453/27, 1453/28, 1453/31, 1453/4
Location: Scottish Marine institute, Scotland, UK

- **Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Nostoc* sp. A12.448
Location: Roscoff, France

- ⊗ **Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Nostoc* sp. BEA 1063B, 1249B, 1559B, 0874B, 1279B, 1605B , 0886B, 1557B, 0877B, 1039B, 1454B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

- ⊗ **Name:** [Algal Research Group, Swansea University](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.
Expertise: Microalgae biotechnology, biomass characterization, upstream and downstream process, chemistry, ecophysiology, engineering, large-scale development, molecular biology. Research expertise with microalgae includes (but is not limited to):

 - *Scenedesmus obliquus* and *Chlorella vulgaris*⁵⁸, *Arthrospira maxima*⁵⁹, *Nannochloropsis* spp.⁶⁰, *Micractinium inermum*⁶¹, *Porphyridium purpureum*^{62, 63}, ***Nostoc* sp.**, *Isochrysis galbana* and over 25 common microalgae species including green algae, diatoms, cyanobacteria and dinoflagellates.

Location: Swansea, UK

- ⊗ **Name:** [IBVF - Instituto de Bioquímica Vegetal y Fotosíntesis, Microalgae Biotechnology Group](#)
Business/organisation: research & development
Expertise: bioenergy, ecophysiology, molecular biology. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Anabaena* sp.^{5,7}, *Porphyridium purpureum*⁵, *Scenedesmus vacuolatus*⁵, ***Nostoc***⁵, *Dunaliella salina*⁸

Location: Sevilla, Spain

26. *Odontella aurita*

A marine diatom with interest as a nutritional supplement, and pharmaceutical applications due to its fatty acid characteristics, in particular the accumulation of polyunsaturated fatty acids ¹⁷⁰.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 1054/1, SCCAP K 1251

26.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 1054/1 ²	System: PBR Medium: f/2 + Si medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 µmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	0.001	0.011	0.2
SCCAP K1251 ¹⁷¹	System: PBR (1.2 L working volume) Medium: Modified L1 medium Temperature: 25±1°C Light: 150 µmol/m ² /s for 1 st two days, then 300 µmol/m ² /s continuous	nd	nd	3.95 <i>(low nitrogen)</i> 5.84 <i>(high nitrogen)</i>
SCCAP K1251 ¹⁷²	System: Glass column (300 mL working volume) Medium: Artificial seawater enriched with L1 medium Temperature: 25±1°C Light: 150 µmol/m ² /s Continuous	nd	nd	6.34 <i>(high nitrogen)</i> 6.58 <i>(high phosphorous)</i>

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

26.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
48% protein ² 5% lipid 20% carbohydrate --- ~25% protein ¹⁷¹ ~10% lipids 60.33% Chrysolaminarin (carbohydrate) --- 15.3% protein ¹⁷² 15.9% lipid 50.4% carbohydrate 47.2 % β -1,3-glucan	30% C ² 5% N C/N ratio 6.5	2.33% fucoxanthin ¹⁷¹ (carotenoid) 60.33% Chrysolaminarin	C14:0 27.2% ² C16:0 7.7% C16:1 18.7% C16:2 3.1% C16:3 5.7% C16:4 3.1% C18:1 1.9% C18:2 1.2% C18:4 0.8% C20:5 22.8% other 7.8%

26.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

-
Name: [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *O. aurita* AC815, AC816
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
-
Name: [Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa CCAP](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *O. aurita* CCAP 1007/3, 1054/1
Location: Scottish Marine institute, Scotland, UK
-
Name: [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *O. aurita* Santec 04, NCC87 D-Od.au. IA1
Location: Roscoff, France
-
Name: [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Odontella* cf. *aurita* BEA 0932B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

- ⊗ **Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Alexandrium minutum*⁴¹, *Alexandrium tamarense*⁴¹, *Bigelowiella natans*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumillum*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros gracilis*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros minus*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros mulleri*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros* sp. *Tenuissimus* like⁴¹, *Chlorella autotrophica*⁴¹, *Chlorella vulgaris*⁴¹, *Chloroarchnion reptans*⁴¹, *Closterium baillyanum*⁴¹, *Cyanophora paradoxa*^{41,42}, *Cylindrotheca closterium*⁴³, *Dunaliella salina*^{41,44}, *Dunaliella* sp.⁴¹, *Dunaliella tertiolecta*^{41,45}, *Emiliana huxleyi*⁴¹, *Haematococcus pluvialis*⁴¹, *Heterocapsa triquetra*⁴⁶, *Isochrysis galbana*⁴¹, *Nitzschia* sp.⁴¹, ***Odontella aurita***⁴¹, *Ostreococcus tauri*⁴¹, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁴¹, *Porphyridium purpureum* (*Porphyridium cruentum*)^{44,47,48}, *Rhodella violacea*⁴¹, *Rhodomonas salina*^{41,49}, *Scenedesmus acutus*⁴¹, *Scenedesmus obliquus*⁴¹, *Skeletonema grethae*⁴¹, *Tetraselmis suecica*⁴¹, *Thalassiosira pseudonana*⁴¹, *Tisochrysis lutea*⁵⁰, *Euglena proxima*⁴¹

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina* (*A. platensis*), from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

27. *Parachlorella kessleri*

A eukaryotic freshwater Trebouxiophyceae strain with potential applications for animal feed, nutritional supplement, and biofuel. It can be cultivated autotrophically, mixotrophically or heterotrophically¹⁷³. *Chlorella kessleri* (Fott & Nováková) is considered to be a synonym of *Parachlorella kessleri*²⁶.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 211/11G, QWY28, GB1

27.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 211/11G ²	System: PBR Medium: Jaworki's medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 µmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	0.36	0.413	2.74
QWY28 ¹⁷⁴ collected from rivers in the district of Harbin city, China	System: Conical flasks Medium: Artificial seawater Temperature: 30°C Light: 200 µmol/m ² /s, L:D cycle nd	nd	0.633±0.027	3.8
QWY28 ¹⁷⁴ collected from rivers in the district of Harbin city, China	System: 500 mL glass vessels, 2.5 % CO ₂ Medium: Raw swine wastewater Temperature: 27-30°C Light: 200 µmol/m ² /s, L:D cycle nd	nd	0.775±0.026	6.2
QWY28 ¹⁷⁴ collected from rivers in the district of Harbin city, China	System: 500 mL glass vessels, 2.5 % CO ₂ Medium: Raw swine wastewater Temperature: 27-30°C Light: 600 µmol/m ² /s, L:D cycle nd	nd	1.150±0.056	9.2

GB1 ¹⁷⁵ GenBank KX151669.1	System: 500 mL flasks (200 mL working volume)	nd	0.176±0.00 (phototrophic)	1.043±0.02 (phototrophic)
	Medium: BG11		1.362±0.01 (mixotrophic)	8.176±0.06 (mixotrophic)
	Carbon source: glucose Temperature: 25±2°C Light: 28 µmol/m ² /s, Continuous		1.311±0.01 (heterotrophic)	7.871±0.09 (heterotrophic)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

27.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
51% protein ² 25% lipid 16% carbohydrate --- 54% carbohydrate ¹⁷⁴ (of which ~35% is glucose) --- 41.29±0.90% protein ¹⁷⁵ 20.14±0.58% lipid 34.15±0.42% carbohydrate	nd	23.6 mg/g total chlorophyll ² 4.1 mg/g total carotenoid --- 9.17±0.11 mg/g Chlorophyll a ¹⁷⁵ 3.98±0.02 mg/g Chlorophyll b 2.60±0.02 mg/g carotenoids	C14:0 1.1% ² C16:0 12.1% C16:1 7.2% C18:0 4.2% C18:1 24.2% C18:2 23.5% C18:3 26.8% C20:0 0.5% other 2.1%

27.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- ☼ **Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Parachlorella* sp. BEA 0045, 0046, 0047B, 0060,
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain
- ☼ **Name:** [Andalusian Center of Science and Marine Technology](#) (CACYTMAR) | [Instituto Universitario de Investigacion Marina](#) (INMAR) at University of Cádiz, Spain
Business/organisation: Higher education, research & development
Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology, genomics, molecular biology, waste water treatment. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
- *Botryococcus braunii*³³, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*³⁴, [*Chlorella vulgaris*, ***Chlorella kessleri***, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Scenedesmus obliquus*]³⁵
Location: Cádiz, Spain

- ⊗ **Name:** [Laboratoire GEnie des Procédés Environnement – Agroalimentaire, GEPEA](#)
Business/organisation: research and development, higher education
Expertise: bioenergy, biotechnology, chemistry, engineering. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - *Chlorella vulgaris*⁹⁰, *Chlorella sorokiniana*⁹¹, *Parachlorella kessleri*⁹², *Nannochloropsis oculata*⁹⁰**Location:** Saint-Nazaire, France

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28. *Picochlorum* sp.

Green microalgae which is able to cope with environmental perturbations, thriving in freshwater as well as in 3-fold the salinity of seawater, and in a wide range of light intensities (80-2000 $\mu\text{E}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$), and temperatures (16-33°C). *Picochlorum* species present huge biotechnological interest since they are characterised by high biomass production, high protein and carotenoid content, and lipid accumulation ¹⁷⁶.

Commonly cultivated strains include: SENEW3, QUCCCM 127.

28.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
nd ¹⁷⁷	System: 400 mL square Pyrex bottles Medium: filter sterilized seawater, enriched with trace nutrients Carbon source: 0.75–1% CO ₂ Temperature: 29–33 °C Light: 900-2000 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, L: D cycle nd	nd	~100 g/m ² /d	nd
QUCCCM 127 ¹⁷⁸	System: DASGIP parallel bioreactor system Medium: supplemented sea water Temperature: 30-45°C Light: 60 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 12h L: 12h D cycle	nd	98.3 (35 °C) 250 (20% CO ₂)	nd

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

28.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
55-58% protein ¹⁷⁸ 24-28% lipid 9-14% carbohydrate	51% C ^t 12% N	~9% total chlorophyll ¹⁷⁷ content	C14:0 0.40-0.59% ¹⁷⁸ C16:0 17.6-22% C16:1 0.19-0.26% C18:0 1.39-1.68% C18:1 1-2.22% C18:2 17.45-24% C20:1 48.55-59.94% C20:5 0.58-1.14% C22:1 0.86-1.11%

28.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- ☼ **Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *P. oculatum* AC142, *P. maculatum* AC627
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- ☼ **Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Picochlorum* sp. CCAP 6079/1
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- ☼ **Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *P. atomus* CCMP508, *P. costavermella* BCC143000, *Picochlorum* sp. (various)
Location: Roscoff, France
- ☼ **Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *P. eukaryotum* BEA 0756B, *P. maculatum* BEA 0741B, *P. oklahemense* BEA BEA 0398, 0399, 0400, 0401, 0402, 0421, 0422, 0654B, 0153B, 0154B, 0155B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

29. *Porphyridium purpureum*

A species of marine red algae belonging to the Porphyridiophyceae family. It presents high potential to produce B-phycoerythrin (B-PE), long chain polyunsaturated fatty acids (LC-PUFAs) and exopolysaccharides (EPS) which are excellent feedstock for food, nutraceuticals and pharmaceuticals ¹⁷⁹. *Porphyridium cruentum* (S.F.Gray) is considered to be a synonym of *Porphyridium purpureum* (Bory) ²⁶.

Commonly cultivated strains include:

SCS-02, CCAP 1380/3, CoE1

29.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
SCS-02 ¹⁸⁰	System: Glass column PBR Medium: ASW medium Temperature: 25±1°C Light: 350 µmol/m ² /s, continuous light	nd	nd	5.54 (high nitrogen)
CCAP 1380/3 ⁶³	System: two 600 L PBRs (one for Batch Culture and another for semi-continuous culture) Medium: f/2 commercial medium (Cell-hi F2P, Varicon) Temperature: those registered in Summer season in Wales (11-22°C) Light: those registered in Summer season in Wales (average of 376.4 µmol/m ² /s)	26.60 (Batch) 47.04 (Semi-continuous)	72.5 (Batch) 145 (Semi-continuous)	0.97 (Batch) 1.04 (Semi-continuous)
CoE1 ¹⁸¹	System: 1 L flasks Medium: ASW, KOCK, Pringsheim II and f/2 medium. Temperature: 25°C	nd	nd	9.95 (ASW medium) 9.25 (Pringsheim II medium)

	Light: from 110 to 220 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, continuous light			8.34 (KOCK medium) 2.58 (f/2 medium)
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

29.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
47.1% protein ¹⁸⁰ (high nitrogen) 12% lipid (high nitrogen) 52.1% carbohydrate (low nitrogen) --- ~ 15-22% protein ⁶³ ~ 17-20% lipid ~ 15-25% carbohydrate	nd	nd	C16:0 ~32% ¹⁸⁰ C16:1 ~2% C18:0 ~1% C18:1 ~2% C18:2 ~11% C20:4 ~27% C20:5 ~15% --- C16:0 13.32% ¹⁸¹ C18:0 2.32% C18:2 8.38% C20:3 1.26% C20:4 9.03% C20:5 2.60% Others 2.90% (220 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 3 L/min of aeration)

29.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- ☼ **Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *P. purpureum* AC120, AC121, AC122
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- ☼ **Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *P. purpureum* CCAP 1380/11, 1380/1A, 1380/3, 1380/5, 1380/9
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom

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- ☼ **Name:** [Algal BioSciences – National University of Ireland](#)
Business/organisation type: research & development
Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Porphyridium purpureum*¹⁸², *Pavlova lutheri*¹⁸³

Location: Galway, Ireland

- ☼ **Name:** [Algal Research Group, Swansea University](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.
Expertise: Microalgae biotechnology, biomass characterization, upstream and downstream process, chemistry, ecophysiology, engineering, large-scale development, molecular biology. Research expertise with microalgae includes (but is not limited to):

 - *Scenedesmus obliquus* and *Chlorella vulgaris*⁵⁸, *Arthrospira maxima*⁵⁹, *Nannochloropsis spp.*⁶⁰, *Micractinium inermum*⁶¹, *Porphyridium purpureum*^{62,63}, *Nostoc sp.*, *Isochrysis galbana* and over 25 common microalgae species including green algae, diatoms, cyanobacteria and dinoflagellates.

Location: Swansea, UK

- ☼ **Name:** [IBVF - Instituto de Bioquímica Vegetal y Fotosíntesis, Microalgae Biotechnology Group](#)
Business/organisation type: research & development
Expertise: bioenergy, ecophysiology, molecular biology. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Anabaena sp.*^{5,7}, *Porphyridium purpureum*⁵, *Scenedesmus vacuolatus*⁵, *Nostoc*⁵, *Dunaliella salina*⁸

Location: Sevilla, Spain

- ☼ **Name:** [LIENSS - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: research and development
Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Alexandrium minutum*⁴¹, *Alexandrium tamarense*⁴¹, *Bigelowiella natans*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans f. pumillum*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros gracilis*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros minus*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros mulleri*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros sp. Tenuissimus like*⁴¹, *Chlorella autotrophica*⁴¹, *Chlorella vulgaris*⁴¹, *Chloroarchnion reptans*⁴¹, *Closterium baillyanum*⁴¹, *Cyanophora paradoxa*^{41,42}, *Cylindrotheca closterium*⁴³, *Dunaliella salina*^{41,44}, *Dunaliella sp.*⁴¹, *Dunaliella tertiolecta*^{41,45}, *Emiliania huxleyi*⁴¹, *Haematococcus pluvialis*⁴¹, *Heterocapsa triquetra*⁴⁶, *Isochrysis galbana*⁴¹, *Nitzschia sp.*⁴¹, *Odontella aurita*⁴¹, *Ostreococcus tauri*⁴¹, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁴¹, *Porphyridium purpureum* (*Porphyridium cruentum*)^{44,47,48}, *Rhodella violacea*⁴¹, *Rhodomonas salina*^{41,49}, *Scenedesmus acutus*⁴¹, *Scenedesmus obliquus*⁴¹, *Skeletonema grethae*⁴¹,

*Tetraselmis suecica*⁴¹, *Thalassiosira pseudonana*⁴¹, *Tisochrysis lutea*⁵⁰, *Euglena proxima*⁴¹

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxins \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina* (*A. platensis*), from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

⊗ **Name:** [Xanthella Ltd.](#)

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Design and test bespoke PBRs, consultancy, repair and recycling of old systems, active research and development. The company has worked on⁵¹:

- *Chaetoceros muelleri*, *Chlamydomonas acidophila*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Dunaliella primolecta*, *Desmodesmus subspicatus*, *Fragilaria* sp., *Isochrysis galbana*, *Limnoraphis robusta*, *Nannochloropsis* sp., *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, ***Porphyridium cruentum***, *Synechocystis* sp., *T-isochrysis lutea*

Location: European Marine Science Park, Argyll, Scotland

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30. *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*

A marine diatom strain with ability to produce high yields of fatty acids including polyunsaturated fatty acids, therefore leading to applications for animal feed, nutritional supplement, and biofuel^{184, 185}.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 1055/1, CCMP 632, PTN0301, CCMP 632.

30.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 1055/1G ²	System: PBR Medium: f/2 + Si medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 µmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	0.084	0.16	3.2
PTN0301 ¹⁸⁶ <i>Isolated from water samples collected in the North Sea</i>	System: 1 L bottles Medium: modified f/2 medium, with air or CO ₂ supply Temperature: 20±1°C Light: 90-110 µmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	nd	nd	1.6 (with CO ₂) 1.0 (with air)
PTN0301 ¹⁸⁶ <i>Isolated from water samples collected in the North Sea</i>	System: open ponds (1000 L) Medium: digestate from anaerobic digestion Temperature: outdoors Light: outdoors	0.041	nd	Between 0.3 and 0.8

CCMP 632 ¹⁸⁷	System: 1 L flasks (800 mL working volume) Medium: mixture of municipal wastewater (MW) and seawater (SW) Temperature: 20±1°C Light: 120 µmol/m ² /s, 12h L: 12h D	nd	0.289±0.0001 (in MW:SW=2:1) 0.238±0.002 (in MW:SW=1:1)	1.04±0.01 (in MW:SW=2:1) 0.97±0.02 (in MW:SW=1:1)
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

30.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
42% protein ² 12% lipid 39% carbohydrate --- <i>Growth on air</i> ¹⁸⁶ 41.5±0.4% protein 26.7±0.0% lipid 9.5±2.3% polysaccharides <i>Growth on CO₂</i> ¹⁸⁶ 33.5±1.0% protein 33.8±3.7% lipid 24.0±0.1% polysaccharides	nd	nd	C14:0 7.5% ² C16:0 12.6% C16:1 23.8% C16:2 4.1% C16:3 8.4% C16:4 2.9% C18:1 1.4% C18:2 2.1% C20:4 0.7% C20:5 30.2% other 6.3% --- C14:0, 6.55±0.32% ¹⁸⁶ C16:0, 19.24±0.19% C16:3+C16:1, 49.41±2.68% C18:0, 0.74±0.10 % C86:2+C18:1, 3.63±0.25% C20:4, 1.15±0.12% C20:5, 17.77±2.23%

30.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

☉ **Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)

Business/organisation type: bio-bank

Strain(s) available: *P. tricornutum* AC171, AC590, AC591

Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France

☉ **Name:** [Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa CCAP](#)

Business/organisation type: bio-bank

Strain(s) available: *P. tricornutum* CCAP 1052/1A, 1052/1B, 1052/6, 1055/1 to 1055/9

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Location: Scottish Marine institute, Scotland, UK

☼ **Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)

Business/organisation type: bio-bank

Strain(s) available: *P. tricornutum* IFREMER, Klaus 11b, Pt1_8.6, *Phaeodactylum* sp.

Location: Roscoff, France

☼ **Name:** [ANFACO-CECOPECA](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae project Lead Coordinator

Business/organisation type: Marketing, research & development and innovation support in food and marine technology.

Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology, marketing, valorisation and functionality of microalgal compounds. Microalgal expertise includes (not limited to)^{39,40}:

- *Chaetoceros calcitrans*, *C. salsugineus*, *Conticribra weissflogii* (synonym of *Thalassiosira weissflogii*), *Isochrysis galbana*, *Nannochloropsis gaditana*, *Pavlova gyrams*, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Rhodomonas lens*, *Tetraselmis chuii*, *Tisochrysis lutea*

ANFACO-CECOPECA offers production of tailor-made microalgal biomass. Read more in the [EnhanceMicroAlgae marketplace](#).

Location: Vigo, Spain

☼ **Name:** [A4F – Algae 4 Future](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: bio-bank, producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Their microalgae track-production (large and pilot scale) includes¹⁷:

- *Arthrospira platensis*, *Chlamydomonas* sp., *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Dunaliella salina*, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Lobosphaera incisa*, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Prorocentrum cassubicum*, *Raphidonema* sp., *Scenedesmus* sp., *Scotiellopsis* sp., *Synechococcus* sp., *Synechocystis* sp., *Tetraselmis* sp., *Thalassiosira weissflogii*, *Tisochrysis lutea*

Locations: Lisbon, Portugal

☼ **Name:** [Andalusian Center of Science and Marine Technology](#) (CACYTMAR) | [Instituto Universitario de Investigacion Marina](#) (INMAR) at University of Cádiz, Spain

Business/organisation: Higher education, research & development

Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology, genomics, molecular biology, waste water treatment. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Botryococcus braunii*³³, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*³⁴, [*Chlorella vulgaris*, *Chlorella kessleri*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Scenedesmus obliquus*]³⁵

Location: Cádiz, Spain

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- ⊗ **Name:** [ABIMS – Analysis and Bioinformatics for Marine Science](#)

Business/organisation: platform, informatics

Expertise: bioinformatics, database, metagenomics, molecular biology, software development, transcriptomics. Research outputs associated to the company, as listed in their publications page, include (but are not limited to):

 - *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*¹⁸⁸, *Synechococcus* sp.¹⁸⁹

Location: Roscoff, France

- ⊗ **Name:** [Bantry Marine Research Station](#)

Business/organisation: producer, research and development

Expertise: aquaculture, environment, nutraceuticals, ecophysiology. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*¹⁹⁰

Location: Cork, Ireland

- ⊗ **Name:** [Department of Chemical and Biological Engineering, The University of Sheffield](#)

Network: [Algal Biotechnology Sheffield Network](#)

Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.

Expertise: Research outputs with microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Scenedesmus subspicatus*⁶⁴, *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*^{61, 65}, *Dunaliella salina*⁶⁵⁻⁶⁷, *Micractinium inermum*⁶⁵, *Chlorella vulgaris*^{68, 69}, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*^{70, 71}, *Nannochloropsis salina*⁶⁶, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*⁷¹

Location: Sheffield, UK

- ⊗ **Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Alexandrium minutum*⁴¹, *Alexandrium tamarense*⁴¹, *Bigeloviella natans*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumillum*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros gracilis*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros minus*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros mulleri*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros* sp. *Tenuissimus* like⁴¹, *Chlorella autotrophica*⁴¹, *Chlorella vulgaris*⁴¹, *Chloroarchonion reptans*⁴¹, *Closterium baillyanum*⁴¹, *Cyanophora paradoxa*^{41, 42}, *Cylindrotheca closterium*⁴³, *Dunaliella salina*^{41, 44}, *Dunaliella* sp.⁴¹, *Dunaliella tertiolecta*^{41, 45}, *Emiliania huxleyi*⁴¹, *Haematococcus pluvialis*⁴¹, *Heterocapsa triquetra*⁴⁶, *Isochrysis galbana*⁴¹, *Nitzschia* sp.⁴¹, *Odontella aurita*⁴¹, *Ostreococcus tauri*⁴¹, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁴¹, *Porphyridium purpureum* (*Porphyridium cruentum*)^{44, 47, 48}, *Rhodella violacea*⁴¹, *Rhodomonas salina*^{41, 49}, *Scenedesmus acutus*⁴¹, *Scenedesmus obliquus*⁴¹, *Skeletonema grethae*⁴¹,

*Tetraselmis suecica*⁴¹, *Thalassiosira pseudonana*⁴¹, *Tisochrysis lutea*⁵⁰, *Euglena proxima*⁴¹

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxins \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina* (*A. platensis*), from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

⊗ **Name:** [PhytoBloom](#)/Necton

Business/organisation: producer, research and development

Expertise: aquaculture, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. Their line of products include culture media for microalgae, and aquaculture food concentrates from¹⁶⁷:

- *Nannochloropsis*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*, and ***Phaeodactylum***

Location: Olhão and Algarve, Portugal

⊗ **Name:** [Sparos](#)

Business/organisation: producer, research and development

Expertise: aquaculture, ecophysiology, genomics. Research outputs associated to the company include (but are not limited to):

- ***Phaeodactylum tricornutum***¹⁹¹, *Tetraselmis* sp.¹⁹², *Nannochloropsis oceanica*¹⁹³

Location: Olhão, Portugal

⊗ **Name:** [Xanthella Ltd.](#)

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Design and test bespoke PBRs, consultancy, repair and recycling of old systems, active research and development. The company has worked on⁵¹:

- *Chaetoceros muelleri*, *Chlamydomonas acidophila*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Dunaliella primolecta*, *Desmodesmus subspicatus*, *Fragilaria* sp., *Isochrysis galbana*, *Limnorphis robusta*, *Nannochloropsis* sp., ***Phaeodactylum tricornutum***, *Porphyridium cruentum*, *Synechocystis* sp., *T-isochrysis lutea*

Location: European Marine Science Park, Argyll, Scotland

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31. *Rhodomonas* sp.

A flagellate unicellular red alga belonging to the class Cryptophyceae with cell size between 9.2 and 9.9 μm . This marine microalga plays a significant role as live food in aquaculture due to its protein, EPA and DHA content ¹⁹⁴. Also a source of phycoerythrin.

Commonly cultivated species and strains include:

Rhodomonas sp. (strain Hf-1)

R. salina (strains CCAP 978/27, CCMP 1319, CS-174, CS-24)

R. lens (strain CMP 739)

31.1 Cultivation characteristics of *Rhodomonas* sp.

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
Hf-1 ¹⁹⁴	<p>System: 200 mL Erlenmeyer flasks</p> <p>Medium: f/2 medium, salinity of 28 psu.</p> <p>Temperature: 20°C</p> <p>Light: 35 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, continuous light.</p>	nd	nd	<p>4.36\pm0.20 x 10⁶ cell/mL (temperature, 24°C)</p> <p>3.74\pm0.28 x 10⁶ cell/mL (salinity, 21 psu)</p> <p>3.60\pm0.49 x 10⁶ cell/mL (light intensity 80 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$)</p> <p>4.57$\pm$0.22 x 10⁶ cell/mL (light colour, White)</p>
nd ¹⁹⁵ from the Dutch aquaculture industry	<p>System: Flat-panel PBR</p> <p>Medium: ASW medium</p> <p>Temperature: (15–20–25–30°C)</p> <p>Light: 60–195–330–495–600 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, continuous light.</p>	nd	1.4 (25°C, 600 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$)	11.25 x 10 ⁶ cell/mL (25°C, 600 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$)

nd ¹⁹⁶ <i>isolated from coastal waters in north-eastern Brazil (state of Paraíba).</i>	System: 500 mL Erlenmeyer flasks Medium: f/2 medium, salinity of 34 psu. Temperature: 21± 2°C Light: 50 µmol/m ² /s, 12h L: 12h D.	nd	nd	11.3 x 10 ⁵ cell/mL (N-sufficient medium) 5.0 x 10 ⁵ cell/mL (N-starved medium)
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

31.2 Biomass characteristics of *Rhodomonas* sp.

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
Protein: ¹⁹⁶ ~ 30 µg/10 ⁶ cell (N-sufficient medium) ~ 25 µg/10 ⁶ cell (N-starved medium) Carbohydrates: ~ 25 µg/10 ⁶ cell (N-sufficient medium) ~ 150 µg/10 ⁶ cell (N-starved medium)	nd	Chlorophyll a: ¹⁹⁶ ~ 1.3µg/10 ⁶ cell (N-sufficient medium) Chlorophyll c: ~ 1.1 µg/10 ⁶ cell (N-sufficient medium) Phycoerythrin: ~ 5.5 µg/10 ⁶ cell (N-sufficient medium)	Σ SFA 13-16% ¹⁹⁵ Σ MUFA 3-7% Σ PUFA (excl. EPA + DHA) 47-56% Σ EPA + DHA 11-22%

31.3 Cultivation characteristics of *R. salina*

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
nd ¹⁹⁷	System: 200 mL Erlenmeyer flasks. Continuous culture (unknown dilution rate), seawater Medium: Conway medium Temperature: 20°C Light: cool white fluorescents, 1,500 lux, continuous light Aeration: mixture air: CO ₂ =98.5:1.5%	nd	nd	nd

CS-24 and CS-174 ¹⁹⁸	System: 1-L Erlenmeyer flasks. Batch mode Medium: Modified f/2 medium: 0.441 or 3.529 mM N, 0.018 or 0.144 mM P; salinity 33 psu Temperature: 19±1 °C and 29±1 °C Light: 100 or 200 μmol/m ² /s, continuous irradiance	nd	CS-24: 0.07 g dry weight/L (3.529 mM N, 0.144 mM P; 200 μmol/m ² /s, 19 or 29 °C) CS-174: 0.105 g dry weight/L (3.529 mM N, 0.144 mM P; 200 μmol/m ² /s, 19 °C)	CS-24: 3.2 x 10 ⁶ cell/mL and 0.7 g dry weight/L (3.529 mM N, 0.144 mM P; 200 μmol/m ² /s, 19 or 29 °C) CS-174: 4.7 x 10 ⁶ cell/mL and 1.05 g dry weight/L (3.529 mM N, 0.144 mM P; 200 μmol/m ² /s, 19 °C)
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

31.4 Biomass characteristics of *R. salina*

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
Total sterol content ¹⁹⁷ 55.68 fg/cell Cholesterol 9.71% Brassicasterol 90.29% ---			Total fatty acids ¹⁹⁷ : 11.34 pg/cell Σ SFA 37.11% Σ MUFA 15.61% Σ PUFA 46.77% EPA 4.78% DHA 3.58% ---
Protein ¹⁹⁹ : CS-24 and CS-174 Max. ~ 55% d.w. (3.529 mM N, 0.144 mM P) Min. ~ 35% d.w. (0.441 mM N, 0.018 mM P)	nd	nd	CS-24 ¹⁹⁹ : Max. Σ SFA ~ 42% (0.441 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 3.529 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 29 °C)
Lipids ¹⁹⁹ : Max. CS-24 ~ 18% d.w. Max. CS-174 ~ 25% d.w. (0.441 mM N, 0.144 mM P, 200 μmol/m ² /s, 19 °C)			Max. Σ MUFA ~ 27% (0.441 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 3.529 mM N & 0.018 mM P, 3.529 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 19 °C)
Min. CS-24 ~ 5% d.w. Min. CS-174 ~ 6% d.w. (0.441 mM N, 0.018 mM P, 200 μmol/m ² /s, 29 °C)			Max. Σ PUFA 55% (0.441 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 200 μmol/m ² /s, 19 °C) Max. EPA 10% (0.441 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 200 μmol/m ² /s, 19 °C) Max. DHA 6.4%

			<p>(3.529 mM N & 0.018 mM P, 200 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 19 °C)</p> <p>CS-174¹⁹⁹: Max. Σ SFA ~ 47% (0.441 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 3.529 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 200 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 29 °C)</p> <p>Max. Σ MUFA ~ 26% (3.529 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 100 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 19 °C)</p> <p>Max. Σ PUFA 55% (0.441 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 200 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 19 °C)</p> <p>Max. EPA 13.2% (0.441 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 200 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 19 °C)</p> <p>Max. DHA 6.5% (0.441 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 200 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 19 °C)</p>
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31.5 Cultivation characteristics of *R. lens*

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCMP 739 ¹³¹	<p>System: 80-mL, 30-mm diameter glass tubes. Semi-continuous culture (10%-20%-30%-40%-50% daily dilution rate)</p> <p>Medium: Algal-1²⁰⁰, salinity 35 psu</p> <p>Temperature: 21±1.5°C</p> <p>Light: cool white fluorescents, 242 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, light:dark cycle of 12 h:12 h</p> <p>Aeration: mixture air:CO₂</p>	nd	0.38 g d.w./L/d (40 % dilution rate)	<p>Max: 22.16 × 10⁶ cells/mL, (10% dilution rate)</p> <p>Min. 7.17 × 10⁶ cells/mL (50% dilution rate)</p>

CCMP 739 ²⁰¹	System: 4-L Erlenmeyer flasks or 10-L polycarbonate carboys. Medium: f/2 medium; salinity 34-35 psu Temperature: room temperature, 22-29 °C Light: natural sunlight	nd	nd	nd
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

31.6 Biomass characteristics of *R. lens*

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
Protein ¹³¹ : Max. 64 pg/cell, 45% of organic fraction (40% dilution rate) Min. 36 pg/cell, 64% of organic fraction (10% dilution rate) Lipids ¹³¹ : Max. ~ 42% of organic fraction (10% dilution rate) Min. ~ 20% of organic fraction (30%-40% dilution rate)	nd	Total chlorophylls ¹³¹ : 1.4-2.0 pg/cell (50% and 40% dilution rate, respectively) Phycoerythrin ¹³¹ : 3.4-8.5 pg/cell (10% and 50% dilution rate, respectively)	Σ SFA max. 54% ¹³¹ (10% dilution rate) Σ MUFA max. 8% (10% dilution rate) Σ PUFA max. 65% (20%-40% dilution rate) EPA max. 9% (20% dilution rate) DHA max. 4% (20% dilution rate) --- Σ SFA ~ 22.2% ²⁰² Σ MUFA ~ 12.3% Σ PUFA ~ 65.5% EPA 11.9% DHA 7.4%

31.5 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- **Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Rhodomonas* sp. AC162
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France

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- ☼ **Name:** [Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa CCAP](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *R. salina* CCAP 978/27, *R. maculata* CCAP 979/14, *R. atrorosea* CCAP 978/6A, 978/6B, *R. baltica* CCAP 979/9, *R. chrysoidea* CCAP 978/6
Location: Scottish Marine institute, Scotland, UK

- ☼ **Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Rhodomonas* sp. (various), *R. salina* CCMP322, AC721, AC160
Location: Roscoff, France

- ☼ **Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Rhodomonas* sp. BEA 0081B, 0223B, 0113, 0113B, 0116B, 0117B, 0121B, 0124, 0689B, 0125B,
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

- ☼ **Name:** [ANFACO-CECOPECA](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae project Lead Coordinator
Business/organisation type: Marketing, research & development and innovation support in food and marine technology.
Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology, marketing, valorisation and functionality of microalgal compounds. Microalgal expertise includes (not limited to)^{39, 40}:
 - *Chaetoceros calcitrans*, *C. salsaugineus*, *Conticribra weissflogii* (synonym of *Thalassiosira weissflogii*), *Isochrysis galbana*, *Nannochloropsis gaditana*, *Pavlova gyrans*, *Phaeodactylum tricorutum*, ***Rhodomonas lens***, *Tetraselmis chuii*, *Tisochrysis lutea*
ANFACO-CECOPECA offers production of tailor-made microalgal biomass. Read more in the [EnhanceMicroAlgae marketplace](#).
Location: Vigo, Spain

- ☼ **Name:** [Aqualgae](#)
Business/organisation: research and development
Expertise: design and installation of high-productivity photobioreactors, suppliers of culturing media, inoculums, and lyophilised cultures of²⁰:
 - *Chlorella*, *Haematococcus*, *Arthrospira*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*, *Pavlova*, *Chaetoceros*, *Skeletonema*, *Nitzschia*, ***Rhodomonas***, *Nannochloropsis***Locations:** Diana do Castelo, Portugal; and A Coruña, Spain

- ☼ **Name:** [Buggypower](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated partner

Business/organization type: producer, research & development, downstream processing

Expertise: feed, food, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. The company specialises in ¹⁰¹:

- *Chlorella*, *Nannochloropsis*, ***Rhodomonas***

Location: Lisbon, Portugal (shared services centre & Alguimya store); Funchal, Portugal (Financial office); Porto Santo, Portugal (Buggypower production unit in partnership with Electricity Company of Madeira); San Pedro del Pinatar, Spain (Financial office); Lorqui, Spain (Research and development pilot plant)

- ⊗ **Name:** [Group of Biotechnology and Aquaculture](#), Universidad de Santiago de Compostela

Business/organization type: research & development, higher education

Expertise: biotechnology, aquaculture. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- [*Dunaliella salina*, *Dunaliella tertiolecta*] ¹²², *Haematococcus pluvialis* ¹²⁶, [*Tetraselmis suecica*, *Tetraselmis* sp.] ¹²⁷, ***Rhodomonas lens*** ¹³¹

Location: Santiago de Compostela, A Coruña, Spain

- ⊗ **Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Alexandrium minutum* ⁴¹, *Alexandrium tamarense* ⁴¹, *Bigelowiella natans* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumillum* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros gracilis* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros minus* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros mulleri* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros* sp. *Tenuissimus* like ⁴¹, *Chlorella autotrophica* ⁴¹, *Chlorella vulgaris* ⁴¹, *Chloroarchnion reptans* ⁴¹, *Closterium baillyanum* ⁴¹, *Cyanophora paradoxa* ^{41,42}, *Cylindrotheca closterium* ⁴³, *Dunaliella salina* ^{41,44}, *Dunaliella* sp. ⁴¹, *Dunaliella tertiolecta* ^{41,45}, *Emiliania huxleyi* ⁴¹, *Haematococcus pluvialis* ⁴¹, *Heterocapsa triquetra* ⁴⁶, *Isochrysis galbana* ⁴¹, *Nitzschia* sp. ⁴¹, *Odontella aurita* ⁴¹, *Ostreococcus tauri* ⁴¹, *Phaeodactylum tricorutum* ⁴¹, *Porphyridium purpureum* (*Porphyridium cruentum*) ^{44,47,48}, *Rhodella violacea* ⁴¹, ***Rhodomonas salina*** ^{41,49}, *Scenedesmus acutus* ⁴¹, *Scenedesmus obliquus* ⁴¹, *Skeletonema grethae* ⁴¹, *Tetraselmis suecica* ⁴¹, *Thalassiosira pseudonana* ⁴¹, *Tisochrysis lutea* ⁵⁰, *Euglena proxima* ⁴¹

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina* (*A. platensis*), from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

32. *Scenedesmus obliquus*

A freshwater green unicellular microalga belonging to the class Chlorophyceae. Its cells can be grouped to form colonies and they are non-motile. It is one of the most widely used lipid-producing microalgae ²⁰³.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
FACHB 416, SJTU-3

32.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
nd ²⁰⁴ <i>from laboratory of live food culture, Institute of Tropical Aquaculture, University Malaysia Terengganu, Malaysia.</i>	System: 1 L Erlenmeyer flasks in outdoor natural conditions Medium: BBM Temperature: 17-34°C Light: nd Environmental light/dark cycle	nd	nd	1.50 x 10 ⁷ (cell/mL)
nd ²⁰⁴ <i>from laboratory of live food culture, Institute of Tropical Aquaculture, University Malaysia Terengganu, Malaysia.</i>	System: 1 L Erlenmeyer flasks, laboratory control conditions Medium: BBM Temperature: 25°C Light: 2000 μmol/m ² /s, Continuous light	nd	nd	2.80 x 10 ⁷ (cell/mL)
FACHB 416 ²⁰⁵	System: 250 mL conical flasks. Medium: BG-11 medium + 0, 25, 50, 100, 200, 500 mg/L	nd	nd	1.60 x 10 ⁷ (cell/mL) (at LAS concentrations <100 mg/L)

	<i>linear alkylbenzene sulfonate (LAS)</i> Temperature: 25°C Light: 50 μmol/m ² /s, 12h L: 12h D			
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

32.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
<i>Outdoor natural conditions</i> ²⁰⁴ 30.7±0.01% protein ~20±0.0% lipid ~20±0.0% carbohydrates <i>Control conditions</i> ²⁰⁴ 37.7±0.02% protein ~37±0.0% lipid 38.2±0.02% carbohydrates --- 26.9 ± 3.8% protein ²⁰⁶ 12.7 ± 1.3% lipid 11.9 ± 1.1% carbohydrate --- 25 mg/L LAS treatment ²⁰⁵ 24.0% lipid	nd	nd	C15:0 3.3% ²⁰⁵ C16:0 22.6% C18:0 1.8% C18:1 8.6% C18:2 3.5% C18:3 47.7% C20:5 10.4% C22:0 2.1%

32.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

-
Name: [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Scenedesmus* sp. BEA 0146/1, 0146/2, 0579B, 0380, 0146B, 0580B, 0381, 0838B, 0333, 0562, 0334, 0354, 0565
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

-
Name: [Algal Research Group, Swansea University](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.
Expertise: Microalgae biotechnology, biomass characterization, upstream and downstream process, chemistry, ecophysiology, engineering, large-scale development, molecular biology.
Research expertise with microalgae includes (but is not limited to):

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- *Scenedesmus obliquus* and *Chlorella vulgaris* ⁵⁸, *Arthrospira maxima* ⁵⁹, *Nannochloropsis* spp. ⁶⁰, *Micractinium inermum* ⁶¹, *Porphyridium purpureum* ^{62, 63}, *Nosctoc* sp., *Isochrysis galbana* and over 25 common microalgae species including green algae, diatoms, cyanobacteria and dinoflagellates.

Location: Swansea, UK

⊗ **Name:** [AlgoSource](#)

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: engineering, large-scale development, industrial ecology. Know-how on *Spirulina* and its principal ingredient phycocyanin. The company is also working on extracting molecules of interest from other microalgae ¹⁰⁰:

- *Spirulina*, *Chlorella*, *Scenedesmus*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*

Locations: Saint-Nazaire, France

⊗ **Name:** [Andalusian Center of Science and Marine Technology](#) (CACYTMAR) | [Instituto Universitario de Investigacion Marina](#) (INMAR) at University of Cádiz, Spain

Business/organisation: Higher education, research & development

Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology, genomics, molecular biology, waste water treatment. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Botryococcus braunii* ³³, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* ³⁴, [*Chlorella vulgaris*, *Chlorella kessleri*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Scenedesmus obliquus*] ³⁵

Location: Cádiz, Spain

⊗ **Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Alexandrium minutum* ⁴¹, *Alexandrium tamarense* ⁴¹, *Bigelowiella natans* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumillum* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros gracilis* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros minus* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros mulleri* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros* sp. *Tenuissimus* like ⁴¹, *Chlorella autotrophica* ⁴¹, *Chlorella vulgaris* ⁴¹, *Chloroarchaon reptans* ⁴¹, *Closterium baillyanum* ⁴¹, *Cyanophora paradoxa* ^{41, 42}, *Cylindrotheca closterium* ⁴³, *Dunaliella salina* ^{41, 44}, *Dunaliella* sp. ⁴¹, *Dunaliella tertiolecta* ^{41, 45}, *Emiliania huxleyi* ⁴¹, *Haematococcus pluvialis* ⁴¹, *Heterocapsa triquetra* ⁴⁶, *Isochrysis galbana* ⁴¹, *Nitzschia* sp. ⁴¹, *Odontella aurita* ⁴¹, *Ostreococcus tauri* ⁴¹, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* ⁴¹, *Porphyridium purpureum* (*Porphyridium cruentum*) ^{44, 47, 48}, *Rhodella violacea* ⁴¹, *Rhodomonas salina* ^{41, 49}, *Scenedesmus acutus* ⁴¹, *Scenedesmus obliquus* ⁴¹, *Skeletonema grethae* ⁴¹, *Tetraselmis suecica* ⁴¹, *Thalassiosira pseudonana* ⁴¹, *Tisochrysis lutea* ⁵⁰, *Euglena proxima* ⁴¹

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

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In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina (A. platensis)*, from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

⊗ **Name:** [uFraction8](#)

Business/organisation type: start-up, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: technology, harvesting. The start-up company is developing technologies suitable for biomass filtration, separation, and de-watering. The start-up has tested their innovative solution with *Scenedesmus*, although their innovative solution can be used for a wide range of microorganisms.

Locations: Falkirk, Scotland

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33. *Scenedesmus quadricauda*

A freshwater green unicellular microalga belonging to the class Chlorophyceae. It can grow in wide range of industrial waste waters with reasonably good adaptation ability ²⁰⁷ and it is considered a versatile biofuel feedstock ²⁰⁸.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
ABU12

33.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
ABU12 ²⁰⁹	System: 200 mL Erlenmeyer flasks Medium: BBM Temperature: 23±2°C Light: 150 µmol/m ² /s, continuous light	nd	nd	~0.75
nd ²⁰⁷	System: 7 L tank. Medium: Wastewater (from Shek Wu Hui Sewage Treatment Works) Temperature: 28°C Light: 7000 lux, 12h L: 12h D	nd	nd	0.995 (acclimated culture) 0.940 (non-acclimated culture)
nd ²¹⁰ from reservoirs in the region of Fez (northern Morocco)	System: Erlenmeyer flasks Medium: synthetic medium Temperature: 20-25°C Light: 300 µmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	nd	~0.99	nd

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

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33.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
<p><i>Acclimated culture</i> ²⁰⁷ ~20.0% lipid</p> <p><i>Non-acclimated cultures</i> ~18.0% lipid</p> <p>---</p> <p>4.38 – 9.55% protein ²¹⁰ 6.91 – 10.60% lipid 3.67 – 24.76% carbohydrates</p>	nd	<p><i>Acclimated culture</i> ²⁰⁷ ~5.5mg/L chlorophyll-a</p> <p><i>Non-acclimated culture</i> ~5.3mg/L chlorophyll-a</p>	<p><i>Acclimated culture</i> ²⁰⁷ C14:0 0.7% C16:0 50.4% C16:1 1.6% C18:0 3.1% C18:1n9 3.0% C18:2n6 24.3% C18:3n3 14.6% C18:3n6 2.3%</p> <p><i>Non-acclimated culture</i> C14:0 0.9% C16:0 55.6% C16:1 2.4% C18:0 1.5% C18:1n9 3.3% C18:2n6 19.9% C18:3n3 14.4% C18:3n6 2.1%</p>

33.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- ⊗ **Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *S. quadricauda* CCAP 276/16, 276/21
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- ⊗ **Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Scenedesmus* sp. BEA 0146/1, 0146/2, 0579B, 0380, 0146B, 0580B, 0381, 0838B, 0333, 0562, 0334, 0354, 0565
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain
- ⊗ **Name:** [AlgoSource](#)
Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: engineering, large-scale development, industrial ecology. Know-how on *Spirulina* and its principal ingredient phycocyanin. The company is also working on extracting molecules of interest from other microalgae ¹⁰⁰:

- *Spirulina, Chlorella, **Scenedesmus**, Tetraselmis, Isochrysis*

Locations: Saint-Nazaire, France

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34. *Selenastrum capricornutum*

A unicellular freshwater green microalga belonging to the class of Chlorophyceae. It presents fast growth and a moderate sensitivity to toxic compounds. *S. capricornutum* has been described as a new promising microalga for biodiesel production due to its fatty acid composition ²¹¹.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
UTEX 1648.

34.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
nd ^u <i>from the laboratory of the Regional Environmental Protection Agency, Perugia Italy (ARPA)</i>	System: 12 L cylindrical photobioreactor Medium: four nutrient solutions and deionized water Temperature: 22 ± 1°C Light: 140 µmol/m ² /s, continuous light	nd	nd	2.4
UTEX 1648 ²¹²	System: 75 L, 40 cm high plastic round containers Medium: f/2 medium Temperature: 23-40°C Light: nd	nd	37.6 g/m ² /d	nd

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

34.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
17.5% lipids ²¹¹ --- 32.3-38.4% protein ²¹² 11.8 ± 34.6% lipid 33-49.8% carbohydrate	nd	nd	C14:0 0.17% ²¹¹ C16:0 19.57% C16:1 0.32% C18:0 1.26% C18:1 54.82% C18:2 4.30% C18:3 6.10% C20:1 0.55% C20:3 1.19%

34.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

-
Name: [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *S. capricornutum* CCAP 278/5
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom

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35. *Tetraselmis subcordiformis*

A marine unicellular green microalga with a cell size of 10–20 µm that is a widely used feed in aquaculture for its high nutrient levels. It has been proven to accumulate starch autotrophically or mixotrophically^{213, 214}.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
FACHB-1751

35.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
FACHB-1751 ²¹⁵	System: 600 mL glass air bubble column PBR (500 mL working volume) Medium: ASW (<i>P</i> deprivation and <i>P</i> repletion) Temperature: 25°C Light: 200 µmol/m ² /s, continuous light	nd	0.68±0.13 (<i>P</i> -deprivation recultivated in <i>P</i> -replete medium)	5.3±0.4 (<i>P</i> -deprivation recultivated in <i>P</i> -replete medium)
nd ²¹⁶ from the Culture Collection of Microalgae at Shanghai Ocean University in China	System: 60 L PBR Medium: f/2 medium Temperature: 15, 20, 25, 30 °C Light: 100 µmol/m ² /s, continuous light	nd	nd	~0.10 d ⁻¹ (at 20°C)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

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35.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
46.9±1.9% starch ²¹⁵ <i>(P-deprivation recultivated in P-replete medium)</i> --- 22.25% lipid ²¹⁶ <i>(at 20°C)</i> --- 18.0 ± 0.3% protein ²⁰⁶ 10.7 ± 0.8% lipid 47.4 ± 1.4% carbohydrate	nd	nd	C16:0 14.93–18.49% ²¹⁶ C16:3n3 6.77–12.30% C18:3n3 15.99–23.65% C20:0 9.04– 10.09%

35.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- ☼ **Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Tetraselmis* sp. AC255, AC260, AC264, AC802
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- ☼ **Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *T. subcordiformis* CCAP 161/1A, 161/1B, 161/3
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- ☼ **Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Tetraselmis* sp. (various)
Location: Roscoff, France
- ☼ **Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Tetraselmis* sp. BEA 0647B, 0076B, 0648B, 0098/1, 1321B, 0098/2, 1323B, 0098B, 0754B, 0758B, 0646B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

- ☼ **Name:** [A4F – Algae 4 Future](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: bio-bank, producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Their microalgae track-production (large and pilot scale) includes ¹⁷:

 - *Arthrospira platensis, Chlamydomonas sp., Chlorella vulgaris, Dunaliella salina, Haematococcus pluvialis, Lobosphaera incisa, Nannochloropsis oceanica, Phaeodactylum tricornutum, Prorocentrum cassubicum, Raphidonema sp., Scenedesmus sp., Scotiellopsis sp., Synechococcus sp., Synechocystis sp., Tetraselmis sp., Thalassiosira weissflogii, Tisochrysis lutea*

Locations: Lisbon, Portugal

- ☼ **Name:** [Algalimento](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated partner
Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Algalimento currently produces all-year round high-quality biomass of ¹²⁵:

 - *Tetraselmis sp., Spirulina canariensis, Dunaliella salina*

Locations: Lisbon, Portugal

- ☼ **Name:** [AlgoSource](#)
Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: engineering, large-scale development, industrial ecology. Know-how on *Spirulina* and its principal ingredient phycocyanin. The company is also working on extracting molecules of interest from other microalgae ¹⁰⁰:

 - *Spirulina, Chlorella, Scenedesmus, Tetraselmis, Isochrysis*

Locations: Saint-Nazaire, France

- ☼ **Name:** [Aqualgae](#)
Business/organisation: research and development
Expertise: design and installation of high-productivity photobioreactors, suppliers of culturing media, inoculums, and lyophilised cultures of ²⁰:

 - *Chlorella, Haematococcus, Arthrospira, Tetraselmis, Isochrysis, Pavlova, Chaetoceros, Skeletonema, Nitzschia, Rhodomonas, Nannochloropsis*

Locations: Diana do Castelo, Portugal; and A Coruña, Spain

- ☼ **Name:** [Group of Biotechnology and Aquaculture](#), Universidad de Santiago de Compostela
Business/organization type: research & development, higher education

Expertise: biotechnology, aquaculture. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- [*Dunaliella salina*, *Dunaliella tertiolecta*] ¹²², *Haematococcus pluvialis* ¹²⁶, [*Tetraselmis suecica*, *Tetraselmis sp.*] ¹²⁷ *Rhodomonas lens* ¹³¹

Location: Santiago de Compostela, A Coruña, Spain

⊗ **Name:** [PhytoBloom](#)/Necton

Business/organisation: producer, research and development

Expertise: aquaculture, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. Their line of products include culture media for microalgae, and aquaculture food concentrates from ¹⁶⁷:

- *Nannochloropsis*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*, and *Phaeodactylum*

Location: Olhão and Algarve, Portugal

⊗ **Name:** [Sparos](#)

Business/organisation: producer, research and development

Expertise: aquaculture, ecophysiology, genomics. Research outputs associated to the company include (but are not limited to):

- *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* ¹⁹¹, *Tetraselmis sp.* ¹⁹², *Nannochloropsis oceanica* ¹⁹³

Location: Olhão, Portugal

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36. *Tetraselmis suecica*

A marine unicellular green microalga. It is a motile chlorophyte that can be used as a feedstock in aquaculture due to its high lipid content. *T. suecica* can be also used to treat wastewater²¹⁷.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CS187

36.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CS187 ²¹⁷	<p>System: 2 L Erlenmeyer flasks</p> <p>Medium: seawater and anaerobically-digested piggery effluent (ADPE)</p> <p>Temperature: 25 ± 1°C</p> <p>Light: 175 µmol/m²/s, 12h L: 12h D cycle</p>	nd	59.8 mg/L/d	nd
nd ²¹⁸ from NLP Corp. (Busan, Korea)	<p>System: 20-L circular cylindrical tank</p> <p>Medium: f/2 medium</p> <p>Temperature: 20 ± 1°C</p> <p>Light: 36.3, 60.5, 84.7, 108.9, 133.1 µmol/m²/s, continuous light</p>	nd	nd	<p>0.89 (at 108.9 µmol/m²/s)</p> <p>1.1 (at 18.5 mg/L Nitrogen)</p>

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

36.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
~30mg/L/d lipid ²¹⁷ ~7mg/L/d carbohydrate --- 17.28% protein ²¹⁸	nd	1.5% chlorophyll ²¹⁷ content	C16:0 ~55.0% ²¹⁸ C18:0 ~1.0% C18:1 ~20.0% C18:2(6) ~2.0% C18:3 ~0.8%

36.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- ☼ **Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *T. suecica* AC254, *Tetraselmis* sp. AC255, AC260, AC264, AC802
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- ☼ **Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *T. suecica* CCAP 66/22A, 66/22B, 66/22C, 66/22D, 66/38, 66/4
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- ☼ **Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *T. suecica* TS-Droze, *Tetraselmis* sp. (various)
Location: Roscoff, France
- ☼ **Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Tetraselmis* sp. BEA 0647B, 0076B, 0648B, 0098/1, 1321B, 0098/2, 1323B, 0098B, 0754B, 0758B, 0646B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain
- ☼ **Name:** [Algalimento](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated partner
Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Algalimento currently produces all-year round high-quality biomass of ¹²⁵:

- *Tetraselmis sp.*, *Spirulina canariensis*, *Dunaliella salina*

Locations: Lisbon, Portugal

☼ **Name:** [AlgoSource](#)

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: engineering, large-scale development, industrial ecology. Know-how on *Spirulina* and its principal ingredient phycocyanin. The company is also working on extracting molecules of interest from other microalgae ¹⁰⁰:

- *Spirulina*, *Chlorella*, *Scenedesmus*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*

Locations: Saint-Nazaire, France

☼ **Name:** [Group of Biotechnology and Aquaculture](#), Universidad de Santiago de Compostela

Business/organization type: research & development, higher education

Expertise: biotechnology, aquaculture. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- [*Dunaliella salina*, *Dunaliella tertiolecta*] ¹²², *Haematococcus pluvialis* ¹²⁶, [*Tetraselmis suecica*, *Tetraselmis sp.*] ¹²⁷ *Rhodomonas lens* ¹³¹

Location: Santiago de Compostela, A Coruña, Spain

☼ **Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Alexandrium minutum* ⁴¹, *Alexandrium tamarense* ⁴¹, *Bigeloviella natans* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans f. pumillum* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros gracilis* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros minus* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros mulleri* ⁴¹, *Chaetoceros sp. Tenuissimus like* ⁴¹, *Chlorella autotrophica* ⁴¹, *Chlorella vulgaris* ⁴¹, *Chloroarchonion reptans* ⁴¹, *Closterium baillyanum* ⁴¹, *Cyanophora paradoxa* ^{41,42}, *Cylindrotheca closterium* ⁴³, *Dunaliella salina* ^{41,44}, *Dunaliella sp.* ⁴¹, *Dunaliella tertiolecta* ^{41,45}, *Emiliania huxleyi* ⁴¹, *Haematococcus pluvialis* ⁴¹, *Heterocapsa triquetra* ⁴⁶, *Isochrysis galbana* ⁴¹, *Nitzschia sp.* ⁴¹, *Odontella aurita* ⁴¹, *Ostreococcus tauri* ⁴¹, *Phaeodactylum tricorutum* ⁴¹, *Porphyridium purpureum (Porphyridium cruentum)* ^{44,47,48}, *Rhodella violacea* ⁴¹, *Rhodomonas salina* ^{41,49}, *Scenedesmus acutus* ⁴¹, *Scenedesmus obliquus* ⁴¹, *Skeletonema grethae* ⁴¹, *Tetraselmis suecica* ⁴¹, *Thalassiosira pseudonana* ⁴¹, *Tisochrysis lutea* ⁵⁰, *Euglena proxima* ⁴¹

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina (A. platensis)*, from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

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⊗ **Name:** [PhytoBloom](#)/Necton

Business/organisation: producer, research and development

Expertise: aquaculture, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. Their line of products include culture media for microalgae, and aquaculture food concentrates from ¹⁶⁷:

- *Nannochloropsis*, ***Tetraselmis***, *Isochrysis*, and *Phaeodactylum*

Location: Olhão and Algarve, Portugal

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37. *Tisochrysis lutea*

A marine flagellate microalga extensively used as a feed stock in aquaculture and commonly known as T-iso. It is genetically distinct from *Isochrysis galbana*, despite seemingly being morphologically identical²¹⁹. *T. lutea* has been recognized as one of the most suitable species for DHA production due to its fast growth and high DHA content (12–14%)²²⁰. It is also obtaining increased interest for fucoxanthin production²²⁰.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCMP1324.

37.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCMP1324 ²²⁰	<p>System: 500-mL Erlenmeyer flask (<i>in experimental setup 1</i>); 1-L bioreactor (<i>in experimental setup 2</i>)</p> <p>Medium: f/2-Si medium</p> <p>Carbon source: glucose, glycerol, and sodium acetate (<i>in experimental setup 1</i>)</p> <p>Temperature: 23°C</p> <p>Light: 3000 lux, 14h L: 10h D cycle</p>	nd	0.02 (growing mixotrophically with glycerol as source of carbon)	1.4 (growing mixotrophically)
nd ²²¹ obtained from NECTON, S.A. (Olhão, Portugal)	<p>System: flat panel photobioreactors</p> <p>Medium: commercial culture medium stock NutriBloom Plus</p> <p>Temperature: 16.5, 20, 25, and 30 °C.</p> <p>Light: 50, 150, 300, and 500 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 18h L: 6h D cycle</p>	nd	0.35 (at 300 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$) 0.42 (at 30 °C)	1.91 (at 300 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$) 1.81 (at 30 °C)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

37.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
36.7% protein ²²² 22.0% lipid 9.4% carbohydrate (<i>phototrophy</i>)	C/N ratio 92.5 ²²⁰	16.39 mg/g ²²¹ fucoxanthin (50 μmol/m ² /s, dilution rate 0.47 d ⁻¹ , 30 °C)	C13:0 0.64–0.80% ²²⁰ C14:0 14.13–17.75% C15:0 0.22–0.39% C16:0 10.17–13.44% C16:1 4.78–11.24% C17:0 0.80–0.92% C18:0 0.30–0.97% C18:1 12.54–13.36% C18:2 9.10–12.28% C18:3 4.86–10.39% C18:4 12.88–14.5% C20:0 0.24–3.07% C22:6 9.37– 13.77%
41.7% protein 19.3% lipid 7.5% carbohydrate (<i>mixotrophy</i>)		7.8 mg/g chlorophyll-a ²²² 4.8 mg/g carotenoids (<i>phototrophy</i>) 18.9 mg/g chlorophyll-a ²²² 4.8 mg/g carotenoids (<i>mixotrophy</i>)	

37.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- ☉ **Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *T. lutea* AC102, AC620
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- ☉ **Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *T. lutea* CCAP 927/14, 927/19,
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- ☉ **Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *T. lutea* Poulet, Caen, T-iso, AC620, AC102, CCMP463, PLY506A, PLY506B, PLY506C, PLY562
Location: Roscoff, France
- ☉ **Name:** [Laboratoire Phycotoxines IFREMER](#)
Business/organisation: research and development, environmental monitoring

Expertise: chemistry, ecophysiology, molecular biology. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- ***Tisochrysis lutea***¹⁶², *Microcystis aeuriginosa*¹⁶³

The research team at IFREMER works in close collaboration with the EnhanceMicroAlgae team at [LIENSs, University of La Rochelle](#), France.

Location: Nantes, France

- ⊗ **Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Alexandrium minutum*⁴¹, *Alexandrium tamarense*⁴¹, *Bigelowiella natans*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumillum*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros gracilis*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros minus*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros mulleri*⁴¹, *Chaetoceros* sp. *Tenuissimus* like⁴¹, *Chlorella autotrophica*⁴¹, *Chlorella vulgaris*⁴¹, *Chloroarchnion reptans*⁴¹, *Closterium baillyanum*⁴¹, *Cyanophora paradoxa*^{41,42}, *Cylindrotheca closterium*⁴³, *Dunaliella salina*^{41,44}, *Dunaliella* sp.⁴¹, *Dunaliella tertiolecta*^{41,45}, *Emiliania huxleyi*⁴¹, *Haematococcus pluvialis*⁴¹, *Heterocapsa triquetra*⁴⁶, *Isochrysis galbana*⁴¹, *Nitzschia* sp.⁴¹, *Odontella aurita*⁴¹, *Ostreococcus tauri*⁴¹, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁴¹, *Porphyridium purpureum* (*Porphyridium cruentum*)^{44,47,48}, *Rhodella violacea*⁴¹, *Rhodomonas salina*^{41,49}, *Scenedesmus acutus*⁴¹, *Scenedesmus obliquus*⁴¹, *Skeletonema grethae*⁴¹, *Tetraselmis suecica*⁴¹, *Thalassiosira pseudonana*⁴¹, ***Tisochrysis lutea***⁵⁰, *Euglena proxima*⁴¹

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina* (*A. platensis*), from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

- ⊗ **Name:** [Xanthella Ltd.](#)

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Design and test bespoke PBRs, consultancy, repair and recycling of old systems, active research and development. The company has worked on⁵¹:

- *Chaetoceros muelleri*, *Chlamydomonas acidophila*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Dunaliella primolecta*, *Desmodesmus subspicatus*, *Fragilaria* sp., *Isochrysis galbana*, *Limnorphis robusta*, *Nannochloropsis* sp., *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Porphyridium cruentum*, *Synechocystis* sp., ***T-isochrysis lutea***

Location: European Marine Science Park, Argyll, Scotland

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Appendix 1. Media recipes

A compilation of the microalgae media recipes shown in this strain catalogue is presented in this appendix. The reader should be aware that recipes shown here follow the standard protocol where culturing medium is prepared by mixing specific quantities of stock solutions so as to reach the desired components' medium concentrations.

Unless otherwise specified, all media is prepared by carrying out the following protocol:

1. Prepare all necessary *stock solutions** by dissolving each component in 1 L of distilled H₂O (dH₂O);
2. Add/mix the corresponding quantity of stock solutions into dH₂O;
3. Bring final volume to 1 L;
4. Adjust pH if required; and
5. Autoclave (sterilize at 15 psi for 15 min).

* Preparation of *stock solutions* is very useful during media preparation as it reduces weighing errors, particularly for those components that are necessary in very small quantities (micronutrients). Whilst we have aimed to provide preparation instructions for stock solutions within all the media recipes presented here, the reader should be aware that stock solution's recipes can be modified accordingly so long as the final medium concentration of each component is met.

It is also important to note that microalgae media recipes have been subject to modifications (e.g. replacing one component for another, increasing or decreasing component concentrations, etc.) to fit the desired cultivation needs, such as optimisation of biomass or metabolite concentration, maximise nutrient uptake, etc. We would therefore encourage the reader to browse the open literature, where different variations of the recipes shown here, as well as many others, have been widely explored.

Useful sources for algal media recipes

- CCAP media recipes ²²³
- Algal Culturing Techniques, by Rober A. Andersen, Elsevier Academic Press (2005) ²²⁴

A.1. Artificial Seawater (ASW) medium

ASW components and concentrations²²³

Component	Stock solution g per 1000 mL H ₂ O	Quantity for 1L medium
<i>Extra salts</i>		3.75 mL
NaNO ₃	30	
Na ₂ HPO ₄	1.2	
K ₂ HPO ₄	1	
<i>Vitamin solution</i>		2.5 mL
Biotin	0.0002	
Calcium pantothenate	0.02	
Cyanocobalamin	0.004	
Folic acid	0.0004	
Inositol	1.0	
Nicotinic acid	0.02	
Thiamine HCl	0.1	
Thymine	0.6	
<i>Soil extract (SE1)</i>	See below	25 mL
Tricine		0.5 g

Soil extract (SE1)

Soil should be air-dried. Dried soil is autoclaved together with a volume of distilled water equivalent to double the volume of soil. Once autoclaved, the supernatant is decanted, filtered (Whatman No 1 paper), and placed in appropriate vessels until used for media preparation. Soil selection is an important consideration for ASW media. Readers are referred to the recipe provided by CCAP ²²³.

A.2. Blue-Green medium (BG11)

Mix stock solutions and bring to 1 L; adjust pH to 7.1 (with NaOH or HCl).

BG11 medium components and concentrations²²³

Component	Stock solution g per 500 mL dH ₂ O	Quantity for 1L medium
NaNO ₃	75	10 mL
K ₂ HPO ₄	2	10 mL
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	3.75	10 mL
CaCl ₂ ·2 H ₂ O	1.80	10 mL
Citric acid	0.3	10 mL
Ammonium ferric citrate green	0.3	10 mL
EDTA·Na ₂	0.05	10 mL
Na ₂ CO ₃	1	10 mL
Trace metals solution	<i>See recipe below</i>	1 mL

Trace metals solution (also known as A5 + Co Trace metals solution)²²³

Component	Quantity per 1L dH ₂ O
H ₃ BO ₃	2.860 g
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	1.810 g
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.220 g
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	0.08 g
Na ₂ MoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	0.39 g
Co(NO ₃) ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.05 g

A.3. Bold's Basal Medium (BBM) and 3N-BBM

The recipe for BBM is presented below. 3N-BBM is identical to BBM medium but requiring 3 times the nitrogen (i.e. 3N) used in BBM.

BBM medium components and concentration²²³

Component	Stock solution g per 400 mL dH ₂ O	Quantity for 1L medium
<i>Macronutrients</i>		
NaNO ₃	10	10 mL
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	3	10 mL
NaCl	1	10 mL
K ₂ HPO ₄	3	10 mL
KH ₂ PO ₄	7	10 mL
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	1	10 mL
<i>BBM trace elements solution</i>	See recipe below	1 mL
<i>Boric acid solution</i>	See recipe below	1 mL
<i>Alkaline EDTA solution</i>	See recipe below	1 mL
<i>Acidified Iron solution</i>	See recipe below	1 mL

BBM trace elements solution²²³

Component	Quantity per 1L dH ₂ O
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	8.82 g
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	1.44 g
MoO ₃	0.71 g
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	1.57 g
Co(NO ₃) ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.49 g

BBM additional solutions²²³

Component	Quantity per 1L dH ₂ O
<i>Boric acid solution</i>	
H ₃ BO ₃	11.42 g
<i>Alkaline EDTA solution</i>	
EDTA	50 g
KOH	31 g
<i>Acidified Iron solution</i>	
FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	4.98 g
H ₂ SO ₄	1 mL

A.4. Chu 13 medium (Modified)

Chu 13 medium components and concentrations ²²⁵

Component	Quantity for 1L medium
KNO ₃	400 mg
K ₂ HPO ₄	80 mg
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	200 mg
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	107 mg
Fe citrate	20 mg
Citric acid	100 mg
<i>Micronutrients</i>	
CoCl ₂	0.02 mg
H ₃ BO ₃	5.72 mg
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	3.62 mg
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.44 mg
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	0.16 mg
Na ₂ MoO ₄	0.084 mg
H ₂ SO ₄ 0.072 N	1 drop

A.5. Conway medium

Conway medium components and concentrations ²²⁶

Component	Quantity for 1L medium
KNO ₃	100 mg
Na ₃ HPO ₄	20 mg
<i>Trace metals</i>	
Na ₂ H ₂ EDTA·2H ₂ O	45 mg
FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	1.3 mg
ZnCl ₂	4.2 mg
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	0.36 mg
CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	4 mg
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	4 mg
(NH ₄) ₆ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ ·4H ₂ O	1.8 mg
H ₃ BO ₃	33.4 mg
<i>Vitamins</i>	
Thiamin HCl	0.2 mg
Cyanocobalamin	0.01 mg

A.6. Detmer medium (DM) modified

Detmer medium components and concentrations ²²⁷

Component	Quantity for 1 L medium
Ca (NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	1 g
KH ₂ PO ₄	0.26 g
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.55 g
KCl	0.25 g
FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.02 g
EDTA·2Na	0.2 g
<i>Trace elements</i>	
H ₃ BO ₃	0.0029 g
ZnCl ₂	0.00011 g
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	0.00181 g
(NH ₄) ₆ MoO ₂₄ ·4H ₂ O	0.000018 g
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	0.00008 g

A.7. f/2 medium

This is a seawater medium, prepared by bringing up the final volume to 1 L with filtered natural seawater. Adjust pH to 8 with 1 M NaOH or HCl.

f/2 medium components and concentrations ²²³

Component	Stock solution qty per 1 L dH ₂ O	Quantity for 1L medium
NaNO ₃	75 g	1 mL
NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·H ₂ O	5.65 g	1 mL
Trace metals solution	<i>See recipe below</i>	1 mL
Vitamins solution	<i>See recipe below</i>	1 mL

f/2 trace metals solution ²²³

Component	Quantity per 1L dH ₂ O
Na ₂ EDTA	4.16 g
FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	3.15 g
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	0.01 g
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.022 g
CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.01 g
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	0.18 g
Na ₂ MoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	0.006 g

Vitamins solution ¹⁰³ (filter-sterilise and store frozen).

Component	Quantity per 1L dH ₂ O
Cyanocobalamin (Vitamin B ₁₂)	0.0005 g
Thiamine HCl (Vitamin B ₁)	0.1 g
Biotin	0.0005 g

A.8. f/2+Si (Guillard's medium for diatoms)

This is a seawater medium, prepared by bringing up the final volume to 1 L with filtered natural seawater. Adjust pH to 8 with 1 M NaOH or HCl.

f/2 + Si medium components and concentrations ²²³

Component	Stock solution g per 1 L dH ₂ O	Quantity for 1L medium
NaNO ₃	75	1 mL
NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·H ₂ O	5.65	1 mL
Trace metals solution	<i>See recipe below</i>	1 mL
Vitamins solution	<i>See recipe below</i>	1 mL
<i>Sodium metasilicate solution</i>		1 mL
Na ₂ SiO ₃ ·9H ₂ O	30 g	

F/2 + Si trace metals solution ²²³

Component	Quantity per 1L dH ₂ O
Na ₂ EDTA	4.16 g
FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	3.15 g
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	0.01 g
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.022 g
CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.01 g
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	0.18 g
Na ₂ MoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	0.006 g

Vitamins solution ²²³ (filter-sterilise and store frozen).

Component	Quantity per 1L dH ₂ O
Cyanocobalamin (Vitamin B ₁₂)	0.0005 g
Thiamine HCl (Vitamin B ₁)	0.1 g
Biotin	0.0005 g

A.9. Jaworski's Medium (JM)

JM medium components and concentrations ²²³

Component	Stock solution g per 200 mL dH ₂ O	Quantity for 1L medium
Ca(NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	4 g	1 mL
KH ₂ PO ₄	2.48 g	1 mL
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	10 g	1 mL
NaHCO ₃	3.18 g	1 mL
<i>EDTA solution</i>		1 mL
EDTA·Fe·Na	0.45 g	
EDTA·Na ₂	0.45 g	
<i>Trace elements solution</i>		1 mL
H ₃ BO ₃	0.496 g	
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	0.278 g	
(NH ₄) ₆ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ ·4H ₂ O	0.2 g	
Vitamins solution	<i>See recipe below</i>	1 mL
NaNO ₃	16 g	1 mL
Na ₂ HPO ₄ ·12H ₂ O	7.2 g	1 mL

Vitamins solution ²²³ (filter-sterilise and store frozen).

Component	Quantity per 200 mL dH ₂ O
Cyanocobalamin (Vitamin B ₁₂)	0.0008 g
Thiamine HCl (Vitamin B ₁)	0.0008 g
Biotin	0.0008 g

A.10. Kuhl medium

Kuhl medium components and concentrations ⁸⁸

Component	Quantity for 1 L medium
KNO ₃	1 g
NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·H ₂ O	0.621 g
Na ₂ HPO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	89 mg
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	246.5 mg
EDTA	9.3 mg
H ₃ BO ₃	0.061 mg
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	14.7 mg
FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	6.95 mg
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.287 mg
(NH ₄) ₆ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ ·4H ₂ O	0.01235 mg
MnSO ₄ ·H ₂ O	0.169 mg
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	0.00249 mg

A.11. SOT medium

Bring final volume to 1 L and adjust pH to 9.

SOT medium components and concentrations ²²⁸

Component	Stock solution g per 1L dH ₂ O	Quantity for 1L medium
NaHCO ₃		16.8 g
K ₂ HPO ₄		0.5 g
NaNO ₃		2.5 g
K ₂ SO ₄		1 g
NaCl		1 g
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O		0.2 g
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O		0.04 g
FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O		0.01 g
EDTA		0.08 g
<i>Trace metal Mix A5</i>		1 mL
H ₃ BO ₃	2.86	
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	1.81	
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.222	
NaMoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	0.39	
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	0.079	
Co(NO ₃) ₂ ·6H ₂ O	49.4 mg	
<i>Trace metal Mix B6 (modified)</i>		1 mL
NH ₄ NO ₃	0.23	
K ₂ Cr(SO ₄) ₄ ·24H ₂ O	96 mg	
NiSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	47.8 mg	
Na ₂ WO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	17.9 mg	
Ti ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	40 mg	

A.12. Sueoka medium

Sueoka medium components and concentrations ⁸⁷

Component	Stock solution g per 1L dH ₂ O	Quantity for 1L medium
KH ₂ PO ₄		0.72 g
K ₂ HPO ₄		1.44
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O		0.02
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O		0.01
NH ₄ Cl		0.5
<i>Trace elements</i>		1 mL
<i>EDTA</i>	10	
H ₃ BO ₃	2.28	
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	4.4	
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	1.02	
FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	1	
CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.32	
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	0.32	
Mo ₇ O ₂₄ (NH ₄) ₆ ·4H ₂ O	0.22	

A.13. Walne's medium

Walne's medium components and concentrations ¹⁴⁹

Component	Stock solution g per 1 L dH ₂ O	Quantity used for 1 L medium
NaNO ₃	100	1 mL
EDTA (Disodium salt)	45	
H ₃ BO ₃	33.6	
NaH ₂ PO ₄ · 4H ₂ O	20	
FeCl ₃ · 6H ₂ O	1.3	
MnCl ₂ · 4H ₂ O	0.36	
<i>Trace metals solution</i>	<i>g per 100 mL</i>	1 mL
ZnCl ₂	2.1	
CoCl ₃ · 6H ₂ O	2	
(NH ₄) ₂ 6MO ₇ O ₂₄ · 4H ₂ O	0.9	
CuSO ₄ · 5H ₂ O	2	
<i>Vitamin solution</i>		1 mL
Thiamine	10	
Cyanocobalamin	10	
Biotin	0.2	

A.14. Zarrouk medium

Zarrouk medium components and concentrations ^{16, 229}

Component	Stock solution g per 1L dH ₂ O	Quantity used for medium
NaNO ₃		2.5 g
K ₂ HPO ₄		0.5 g
K ₂ SO ₄		1 g
NaCl		1 g
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O		0.2 g
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O		0.04 g
FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O		0.01 g
EDTA		0.08 g
NaHCO ₃		16.8 g
<i>Micronutrient solution</i>		1 mL
H ₃ BO ₃	2.86	
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	1.81	
ZnSO ₄ ·4H ₂ O	0.222	
Na ₂ MoO ₄	0.0177	
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	0.079	

Appendix 2. Culture collections

Acronym	Name	Link
AC	Algobank-Caen Université de Caen Normandie <i>France</i>	Click here
BEA	Spaniard Algae Bank (Banco Español de Algas) <i>Spain</i>	Click here
CCAP	Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa at Scottish Association for Marine Science <i>UK</i>	Click here
CPCC	Canadian Phycological Culture Centre Canada <i>Formerly known as the University of Toronto Culture Collection (UTCC) of Algae and Cyanobacteria</i>	Click here
CSMA	Culture Collection of the Centro di Studio dei Microrganismi Autotrofi <i>Italy</i>	n/a
IBVF	Biological Culture Service of the Institute of Plant Biochemistry and Photosynthesis <i>Spain</i>	Click here
LEGE-CC	Blue Biotechnology and Ecotoxicology Culture Collection at CIIMAR <i>Portugal</i>	Click here
NCMA <i>Formerly CCMP</i>	National Center for Marine Algae and Microbiota at Bigelow Laboratory <i>USA</i> <i>Formerly known as the Culture Collection of Marine Phytoplankton (CCMP)</i>	Click here
NIES	National Institute for Environmental Studies <i>Japan</i>	Click here
PCC	Pasteur Culture Collection of Cyanobacteria <i>France</i>	Click here
RCC	Roscoff Culture Collection <i>France</i>	Click here
SAG	Sammlung von Algenkulturen der Universität Göttingen / Culture Collection of Algae at Göttingen University <i>Germany</i>	Click here
SCCAP	Scandinavian Culture Collection of Algae & Protozoa at The University of Copenhagen <i>Denmark</i>	Click here
UTEX	Culture Collection of Algae at The University of Texas at Austin <i>USA</i>	Click here

Appendix 3. List of images

1. *Anabaena cylindrica*²³⁰

2. *Ankistrodesmus falcatus*²³²

3. *Arthrospira platensis*²³⁴

4. *Auxenochlorella protothecoides*²³⁶

5. *Botryococcus braunii*¹⁵⁴

6. *Chaetoceros calcitrans*²³⁹

7. *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*²⁴¹

8. *Chlorella sorokiniana*²⁴³

9. *Chlorella vulgaris*²⁴⁵

10. *Chlorella zofingiensis*²⁴⁷

11. *Cryptothecodinium cohnii*²³¹

12. *Desmodesmus subspicatus*²³³

13. *Dunaliella salina*²³⁵

14. *Dunaliella tertiolecta*²³⁷

15. *Euglena gracilis*²³⁸

16. *Galdieria sulphuraria*²⁴⁰

17. *Graesiella* sp.²⁴²

18. *Haematococcus pluvialis*²⁴⁴

19. *Isochrysis galbana*²⁴⁶

20. *Jaagichlorella luteoviridis*²⁴⁸

21. *Lyngbya lutea* ²⁴⁹

22. *Microchloropsis salina* ²⁵¹

23. *Microcystis aeruginosa* ²⁵³

24. *Nannochloropsis oculata* ²⁵⁵

25. *Nostoc* sp. ²⁵⁷

26. *Odontella aurita* ²⁵⁹

27. *Parachlorella kessleri* ²⁶¹

28. *Picochlorum* sp.

29. *Porphyridium purpureum* ²⁶²

30. *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* ²⁶³

31. *Rhodomonas* sp. ²⁶⁴

32. *Scenedesmus obliquus* ²⁵⁰

33. *Scenedesmus quadricauda* ²⁵²

34. *Selenastrum capricornutum* ²⁵⁴

35. *Tetraselmis subcordiformis* ²⁵⁶

36. *Tetraselmis suecica* ²⁵⁸

37. *Tisochrysis lutea* ²⁶⁰

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